

SafeHabitus

Deliverable D3.2

**Causes and consequences of occupational
injuries and ill health among farmers and
farm workers**

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Acronyms

EU – European Union

CAP – Common Agricultural Policy

CoP – Community of Practice

FTA – Fault Tree Analysis

FSP – Farm Safety Partnership

HSA – Health and Safety Authority

OSH – Occupational Safety and Health

RTA – Reflexive Thematic Analysis

SEM – Socioecological Model

SME - Small and medium enterprises

TN – Technical Note

1. Executive Summary

Introduction

Agriculture remains one of Europe's most hazardous occupations, with farmers facing fatal accident rates higher than most other sectors. Despite decades of safety interventions and regulatory frameworks, progress in reducing farm injuries and fatalities has been uneven. The heterogeneity of European agriculture amplifies these challenges, as farming systems vary dramatically. Across the European Union, agricultural workers experience diverse and persistent occupational health and safety challenges, and a rapidly changing sector facing policy, climate, and economic changes. Understanding root causes and broader consequences of farm safety challenges requires identifying the connections between these immediate occupational risks and higher-level socioeconomic changes and is essential for developing effective interventions.

Objectives

In line with the objectives set out in the original call text this research seeks to enhance understanding and awareness by policy makers, farmers organisations, trade unions and health authorities of farmers' and farm workers' health and safety, and on the implications of the perceptions of their work on the future of the sector and hence on long-term food security; improve policy and governance frameworks favouring safer and more inclusive working environments for farmers and farm workers; and improve health, safety and labour conditions in farming thanks to better performing European and national policy and legal frameworks. In line with these expected outcomes and Task 3.2 description, this deliverable reports a multi-country qualitative research task with the following objectives:

1. Identify national root causes, wider consequences, and potential solutions to critical farm health and safety challenges, and key populations impacted by these challenges across 11 Communities of Practice across the EU.
2. Identify common and overarching themes across all regional reports to develop a socioecological assessment of farm safety challenge causality across the EU to support programme implementation and policy decisions.

Methods

This research employed qualitative methods including focus groups, expert interviews, and stakeholder consultations across 11 European countries—Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, and Spain—each examining specific safety challenges affecting key farming populations through the Socioecological Model (SEM) framework. The methodology was adapted from the originally planned Survivor Stories approach to an Expert Focus Group approach following ethical review (Deliverable 8.1), enabling examination of safety challenges through expert knowledge while protecting participant and researcher wellbeing. Across all 11 CoPs, 65 participants were sampled as part of Focus Groups and Interviews following ethical guidelines. CoPs identified priority regional challenges from their Needs Register and key populations impacted by these challenges, then conducted focus groups identifying root causes, wider consequences, and potential solutions. CoPs coded and analysed collected data using Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) structured around the SEM, reporting procedures and results in Technical Notes. The second stage of analysis consisted of cross-national synthesis of secondary data reported across 11 Technical Notes to identify meaningful patterns and interrelationships between socioecological levels.

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Findings

This SEM analysis of the causes, consequences, and solutions to 11 regionally important farm safety challenges across Europe identified 6 key findings:

1. The socioecology of causes and consequences in the European agricultural systems is hierarchical, with higher level decisions causing consequences at subsequent levels of the SEM, eventually impacting the health and safety of farmers, families, and workers at the lowest levels.
2. Time is the primary resource exchanged between levels, with systemic time poverty as the central exacerbating root causal factor for farm health and safety challenges in this dataset.
3. Regulatory safety culture is responsible for intergroup divisions and non-compliance within the agricultural system and shifting to a cultural approach to safety can protect workers' time and encourage compliance.
4. Cross-stakeholder-collaboration is the most straightforward way to improve the efficiency of support systems as a whole, and address many of the causal factors at higher levels before they are passed to farmers.
5. Technology, especially digitisation, is important but is not guaranteed to increase farm efficiency and can reinforce existing inequalities and deepen farmers' time poverty if poorly implemented.
6. Gender inequalities highlight how the agricultural system's hierarchical nature can result in unfair treatment, poor working conditions, and unequal distribution of labour and time for some populations.

Policy Recommendations

The six key findings from this analysis point toward specific policy reforms and practice changes that can address the hierarchical causation and systemic time poverty affecting European farmers' health and safety. We organise our recommendations according to their implementation pathway, recognising that meaningful improvement requires action at multiple levels and timescales.

Tier 1: Immediate Opportunities (2023-2027)

These recommendations can be implemented within existing frameworks:

- **Gender-disaggregated safety data:** Eurostat and national statistical offices should systematically collect and report farm injury data disaggregated by gender, employment status, and farm type.
- **Farm Safety Communities of Practice:** Member States should utilise existing LEADER funding and EIP-AGRI mechanisms to establish cross-stakeholder farm safety partnerships, building on the model demonstrated by the Irish Farm Safety Partnership.
- **Time-use in advisory services:** Farm Advisory Services should incorporate labour efficiency and work organisation guidance as standard components, drawing on research demonstrating connections between working hours, safety, and profitability.

Tier 2: Post-2027 CAP Integration (2028-2034)

These recommendations align with the proposed Post-2027 CAP framework and should be considered during ongoing legislative negotiations:

- **Time poverty impact assessment:** The Commission and Member States should assess the time burden implications of new CAP measures during design, ensuring administrative requirements do not exacerbate time poverty and associated safety risks.
- **Investment support priorities:** Member States should prioritise support for infrastructure and technologies that demonstrably reduce working time, with particular attention to small and medium farms.

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- **Replacement worker schemes:** Member States should establish or expand relief services enabling farmers to take time for rest, training, and health appointments without compromising farm operations. Schemes should include emergency coverage following farm accidents to prevent the intensification of consequences within farm households.
- **Knowledge transfer on work organisation:** CAP knowledge transfer provisions should explicitly include labour efficiency as a priority topic, recognising this as foundational to farm sustainability and farmer wellbeing.
- **Thematic Network on post-injury support:** The Commission should fund a Horizon Europe Thematic Network to identify and share good practices for supporting farmers and farm households coping with the longer-term burden of injury, building on the SafeHabitus Communities of Practice model.

Tier 3: Longer-Term Vision

Our findings point toward a more fundamental need: integrating farmer health, safety, and wellbeing as explicit objectives of agricultural policy. This would require:

- Recognition of time as a policy-relevant resource, with temporal impact assessment for new measures
- Cross-DG coordination between AGRI, EMPL, and SANTE on farm safety outcomes
- Extension of occupational safety and health frameworks to better cover self-employed farmers
- Institutional mechanisms supporting farmers' access to rest and recovery
- Policy responses that address consequences of injuries as well as causes, including support for injured farmers and their households
- Research investment in understanding how injury consequences cascade through socioecological levels and intensify over time

Full implementation of this vision extends beyond the CAP alone, requiring coordination across multiple policy domains. However, the Post-2027 CAP reform provides an immediate opportunity to embed temporal considerations and safety awareness within agricultural policy design.

2. Introduction

2.1 Background and Context

Despite decades of safety interventions and improvements to farming safety governance frameworks, progress in reducing farm injuries and fatalities is hampered by the complex nature of Agriculture's rapid sectoral change, complex occupational risks, and heterogenous physical and policy geographies across the EU. Agricultural work is mentally, physically, and socially challenging; this can pose major risks to farmers occupational safety and health (OSH). Farmers work up to and sometimes more than 80 hours per week during peak periods, often managing heavy machinery and dangerous livestock (Brennan et al., 2022). Furthermore, most European farmers are self-employed on family operated farms which means that such farms are managed individually from an OSH perspective (Deliverable 3.1). As a result, agriculture remains one of Europe's most hazardous occupations, with a recent SafeHabitus analysis estimating that the annual fatality rate is 545 workers, more than 170% of the reported number (Deliverable 3.1).

While serious accidents and injuries are the most drastic and visible occupational risks, farmers may experience multiple chronic risks as well. Many farmers, particularly women, face steep declines in their ability to work beginning as early as their 40's (Karttunen & Rautiainen, 2013; Conway and O'Mullane, 2025). Musculoskeletal disease (MSD) is one of the most common OSH risks for farmers, with 90% of farmers facing MSD in their lifetime (Osborne et al, 2012). Other important OSH hazards that farmers face include persistent work strain, respiratory diseases, noise exposure, and ultraviolet radiation (Molina-Guzman & Rios-Osorio, 2020). Farmers also face challenges to their social wellbeing, with long working schedules, rural localities, and fragmenting communities leading to persistent isolation (Firnhaber et al., 2024; Brennan et al., 2022; Wheeler et al., 2023). Farmers also face mental health risks, especially stress-related challenges like high levels of burnout (O'Connor et al., 2025; Reissig et al., 2019) as well as depression and anxiety (Torske et al., 2016). This overview captures only a fraction of the literature documenting the many OSH risks European farmers can face.

However, these various OSH hazards are not isolated events but shaped by wider social and economic processes. European farmers also face high-level challenges in economic pressures, policy and governance change, and climate change, which can also threaten their wellbeing and safety (Deliverable 4.1). Broadly speaking, farmers are vulnerable to constant and unpredictable external pressures; changing regulatory and policy priorities, threats of disease and crop failures, rapidly intensifying weather events, and global climate change, and constantly shifting market prices for agricultural goods (Brennan et al., 2022; Donohoe et al., 2024). These high-level factors are not just distal contextual events but deeply connected to farmers' own wellbeing. Indeed, sectoral unpredictability itself can be an important stressor, especially when farmers' income is affected (Firnhaber et al., 2024). While some farmers, especially those who own larger farms or have higher income, may be able to weather these changes, smaller farmers and older farmers may be more vulnerable (Kurlavicius et al., 2024).

Effectively, farmers' immediate OSH concerns are well established in specific EU national contexts. Additionally, there is widespread agreement that these causes are at least somewhat driven by broader socioeconomic changes. An important gap remains to tie these together in a multi-level analysis; to explain how the immediate factors and broader socioeconomic factors may together shape farmers OSH risks, and how. Even more, there are very few studies on the consequences of these OSH risks - beyond the documentation of the health issue itself in either research findings or as a national-level statistic - and even fewer examining these consequences through a multilevel lens.

The Socio-Ecological Model (SEM; see Bronfenbrenner, 2000; Kilanowski, 2017) is a useful theoretical framework to investigate these multi-level dimensions of farm safety. The SEM was designed out of Bronfenbrenner's original Ecological Systems Theory, designed to describe how human development and

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behaviour is shaped by broader social contexts. In this theory, each system includes different domains which contextualise a person's growth: the individual (thoughts, knowledge, and behaviour), microsystem (their work, school, or family), mesosystem (reflecting the overlap of micro- and exosystems), exosystem (local governments and media), macrosystem (economic system and cultural norms), and chronosystem (reflecting all system's change over time). Since then, the SEM was developed as a more generalisable tool for analysing the broader context around other aspects of human behaviour across five similar levels: individual, interpersonal (relationships, social networks, family dynamics), organisational (workplace structures, practices, resources), community (social norms, local institutions, cultural contexts), and policy (economic systems, governance structures) (Lee et al., 2017). Applied to agricultural OSH, this framework allows individual farmers' behaviour to be contextualised by other domains that shape farmers available choices and perceived options. For example, a farmer may use old and faulty equipment not because they enjoy risk-taking (individual level) but because heavy workloads on the farm (organisational level) and a lack of grants to upgrade (policy level) make it infeasible to do otherwise. Therefore, applying the SEM enables identification of how actions or conditions at one level create vulnerabilities or constrain choices at others, allowing for an analysis of causes and consequences of farmer's and farmworkers' health and safety across the EU's varied farming contexts.

2.2 Objectives

To support policy stakeholders and policy makers at national and EU levels, the SafeHabitus project was tasked with (1) improving the understanding OSH challenges on farms and (2) developing policy options that enhance these working conditions and improve the attractiveness of farming. To contribute to these aims, we developed the following objectives to be completed as part of SafeHabitus task 3.2:

1. Identify national root causes, wider consequences, and potential solutions to 11 critical farm health and safety challenges, and key populations impacted by these challenges across 11 Communities of Practice across the EU
2. Identify common and overarching themes across all regional reports develop a Socioecological assessment of farm safety challenge causality across the EU to support programme implementation and policy decisions

Objective 1 is accomplished by undertaking case studies in each of the 11 SafeHabitus Community of Practice (CoP) countries to identify priority farm health and safety challenges from their Needs Register (reported in D3.3), and a key population group impacted by this challenge. Then CoP countries conducted Focus Groups and supporting qualitative data analysis (detailed in section 3.2) to identify the socioecology of these safety challenges. Objective 2 is accomplished by a cross-national qualitative analysis of the secondary data generated to meet Objective 1 and documented by the current deliverable. We report these results in section 4.

This deliverable synthesises findings from 11 European countries: Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, and Spain - each examining specific safety challenges affecting key farming populations. By analysing these diverse national contexts through a common theoretical framework, this work identifies both shared patterns and context-specific variations in how farm safety problems emerge and persist.

This research exemplifies the core approach of the SafeHabitus project; that farmers' and farm workers' health and safety is supported by the stakeholders, organisations, and institutions around them. This deliverable constitutes a comprehensive analysis of these interconnections, presenting detailed synthesis of causes, consequences, and solutions across socioecological levels. By illuminating these patterns that shape farmers OSH and their underlying mechanisms, this research aims to inform policy development, advisory/extension practice, and research directions to ensure the social sustainability of the European agricultural sector.

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2.3 Contribution to Expected Outcomes for SafeHabitus

This deliverable contributes directly to the expected outcomes established in the original call for proposals. Through multi-country qualitative research across 11 Communities of Practice, the analysis advances Outcome 1 by enhancing understanding of both the systemic causes and wider consequences of occupational injuries and ill health among farmers and farm workers. The identification of time poverty as a central causal factor, alongside findings on hierarchical causation within agricultural systems, provides an evidence-based framework for policy makers, farmers' organisations, trade unions, and health authorities. Critically, the analysis documents how consequences flow upwards through socioecological levels—from individual injuries generating household labour crises, to accumulated impacts straining community resources and threatening sectoral labour supply—and intensify within levels through self-reinforcing cycles. This illuminates the broader implications of farm safety challenges for sectoral viability and long-term food security.

The deliverable supports Outcomes 2 and 4 through tiered policy recommendations informed by this causal and consequential analysis. Understanding how consequences cascade and intensify enables identification of intervention points that can break negative cycles. Immediate recommendations address data collection and advisory service integration within existing frameworks, while medium-term recommendations align with Post-2027 CAP negotiations to embed safety considerations within agricultural policy design. The longer-term vision for cross-DG coordination provides a roadmap for systemic improvement of European and national policy frameworks, ultimately contributing to safer and more sustainable working conditions across the agricultural sector.

3. Methods

3.1. Collecting Ethical Data

A primary goal of the SafeHabitus project is to not only produce high-quality research but (through the CoP's) to engage in research activities that support the wellbeing and development of local farming communities. To protect all involved in this research and achieve our central objectives, we adapted the original methodology from the collection and analysis of individual Survivor's Stories about first-hand experiences of farm injuries and safety challenges, to what this deliverable reports: an Expert Focus Group approach (supported by other qualitative data collection) that draws on the Socioecological Model to identify the root causes and wider consequences of injuries.

Originally, this research task involved collecting 50 Survivor Stories (audio-visual case studies) of farm workplace injury and illness incidents; and then assessing the impact of injury and ill health cases by type of labour force involved (age, gender, family, local, external etc.) on the individual, the farm business and society. This data collection effort consisted of CoP's (1) coordinating a local call for video testimonials of people who had experienced accidents, injuries, or other safety challenges in their respective regions, (2) supporting participants' development of these videos, and then (3) analysing these personal experiences of injury. As survivor stories would contain significant sensitive content, we coordinated a thorough ethical evaluation of this task led by SafeHabitus Ethics Mentor Professor Sally Shortall. This evaluation (see Deliverable 8.1) raised potential ethical issues, including concerns around protecting the wellbeing of participants and researchers during conversations about personal injury experiences.

To follow these recommendations, we redesigned this methodology as a Focus Group, supported by interviews and other qualitative data collection (See table 1 in section 3.2 below). While this redesign involved a shift in timelines (from month 30 to 36), it resulted in a comprehensive design with clear guidelines in place to protect researchers and participants' wellbeing throughout the process while ensuring the primary research questions were answered.

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Primarily, we shifted the subject of analysis and therefore the empirical data produced from participants' *personal experiences of injury* to participants' *descriptions of root causes and wider consequences of safety challenges*, with several important consequences. First, this shift no longer required participants to have any personal experience with farm accidents, injuries, or other safety challenges – a point that was made clear to researchers (see Annex 1 for Guidance provided to CoP leaders) and participants during both recruitment and data collection (see Annex 2 for consent materials). As a result of widening this scope beyond solely personal experiences of injury, CoP leaders could tailor the subject of their analysis to the most regionally important farm safety challenge or challenges as previously identified in their Needs Register (see Deliverable 3.3), more effectively building on previous work and integrating tasks across the project.

This broader potential dataset including many different challenges at multiple levels (e.g. Housing as a major safety need for Spain and Machinery Safety as a safety need for Ireland) necessitated a shift in our analytical strategy. Originally, with participants primarily describing their personal experiences, FTA was designed as the primary analytical lens due to its utility in identifying the root factors and chains of causality within a dataset (see Ehiaggina et al., 2022). However, with experts directly discussing the causal and consequential factors at multiple levels, FTA was no longer necessary as an analytical framework to identify these. Instead, we used SEM's multi-level lens to both categorise participants' described causes and consequences and identify patterns across and between factors.

With these primary ethical concerns and subsequent design implications addressed, we implemented our redesigned multi-actor qualitative research study to gather expert knowledge on the causes and consequences of - as well as potential solutions to - farm safety challenges across partner countries. To do so, we first obtained institutional ethical approval from the Teagasc Social Research Ethics Counsel to cover all data collection, handling, storage, and other related activities related to this research across all CoP partners as detailed in D7.2). This institutional review provided an additional layer of protection for participants and researchers by evaluating the redesigned focus group methodology. Importantly, this ethics application covered data collection through both focus groups and other one-on-one methods, such as interviews, to allow partner flexibility and tailoring of the research task to CoP's capacity. In both cases, the subject matter remained the same, and personal experience with the regional safety challenge was not included as inclusion criteria or subject of the interview. Furthermore, this institutional ethical review clarified the role of the primary author, with experience in conducting qualitative research on sensitive topics (e.g. severe mental health concerns) as a safeguard of participant and researcher wellbeing at each stage of development, management, and analysis of this project.

3.2. Procedures

Multi-Actor Approach: CoP Coordination

After this task was designed in full, Teagasc held an online Clinic on 14 May, 2025 to outline this task and incorporate partner feedback into the guidance document (see Annex 1) delivered afterwards. Most importantly, this Clinic outlined the core methodology for completing this multi-actor data collection and analysis project through the CoP's:

1. the CoP's identify the primary analytical subject, priority regional challenges to farm health and safety from their work on the Needs Register (Deliverable 3.3), and key populations impacted by these challenges (e.g. farmers, farm workers including women, seasonal and migrant workers, children, elderly farmers, and other populations).
2. The CoP's undertake translation of the support documents (consent and focus group guide) into the native language and adapt the schedule for use to investigate the specific safety challenge and affected population.
3. The CoP's recruit participants with expert knowledge on the regional challenge or the affected population to attend a Focus Group (e.g. health professionals, farm safety inspectors, farm advisors, farm/worker

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support organisations, co-operatives, producer organisations). Importantly, personal experience of these safety issues was not an inclusion criteria.

4. The CoP's hold a meeting online or in-person with this group. After establishing participants' consent using the translated consent forms, CoPs conduct a Focus Group identifying the root causes, wider consequences, and potential solutions to their chosen topic following their translated and adapted guide. CoPs then capture the data for analysis through notetaking and recording / transcription if possible or if participants agreed to be recorded.
5. The CoP's code and analyse the collected data using an analytical plan described in the Guidance document: a simplified Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) structured around the SEM.
6. The CoP's report their procedures (including any important adjustments made to the research programme outline in the guidance document) as well as their results, in a Technical Note (TN9) following a provided outline/reporting template. These TNs were then revised and improved through consultation with the primary author. The final TNs provide in-depth and multi-level analysis of these regional cases, which served as the basis for Practice Abstracts (PA9) reported in Deliverable 1.6. These TNs together form the first stage of analysis and established a dataset for further synthesis and cross-national analysis.
7. As the lead partner, Teagasc conducts the second stage of analysis consisting of a cross-national RTA and synthesis of secondary data to identify meaningful patterns and interrelationships between socioecological levels identifiable across TN's.

In addition to outlining this process through the Clinic and Guidance documents, CoP's were encouraged to stay in communication with Teagasc/the lead author to ensure that research activities proceeded in a way that satisfied the central research objectives *and* were flexible enough to allow for regional adaptation of methodology (within the bounds of established ethical guidelines). This resulted in a variety of data collection procedures that were tailored to the regional context and delivered suitable secondary data for cross-national analysis.

Across all 11 CoPs, 65 participants were sampled as part of Focus Groups and Interviews (see table 1). These 65 participants were recruited as part of SafeHabitus task 3.2 and followed all subsequent guidelines proposed. As part of their regional reports, two CoPs included additional aligned research efforts from their organisation with an additional 75 participants. Specifically, Germany supported their interviews about tractor seatbelt safety with a public opinion poll deployed across the Agrarscouts network's social media. France supported their expert interview with additional focus group data from a previous study on ergonomics. The individual TNs of these countries delineate the findings from these separate data collection efforts. As these were not Focus Groups or Interviews, but separate synergistic institutional actions, they were not covered under the ethical constraints of the current task. Therefore, while we report these efforts as part of TN9, these sections of the TNs were not included in the coding stage of the current secondary data analysis.

Table 1: Data collection strategies

Country	Data Collection Strategy	Format/Venue	Participants Sampled
Finland	Interviews with farmers	In-person, phone, and online	7
Ireland	Focus Group with farmers, advisors, academics, policymakers, and other health and safety stakeholders	In-person	11
Estonia	Focus Group with farmers	In-person	5

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Lithuania	Interviews with farmers and advisors	In-person	4
Poland	Interviews with farmers, advisors, academics, and safety specialists	Online	5
Germany	Interviews with farmers and safety experts Supported by open ended polling across social media	In-person and Online	7 interviews 64 poll responses
France	Interview with a safety expert Supported by a Focus Group held with a discussion group	In-person	1 interview 11 person focus group
Spain	Interviews with NGO stakeholders and local producers	In-person	6
Slovakia	Interviews with farmers and safety specialists	In-person	7
Slovenia	Interviews with farmers and mental health experts	In-person and online	6
Romania	Focus group with farmers, vets, and safety experts	In-person	6

Materials

To design the script for this study, we drew on FTA (Ehiaggina et al., 2022) and SEM (Bronfenbrenner, 2000; Kilanowski, 2017). While very different theories in scope, the SEM and FTA are both used to highlight relationships between individual-level actions and structural or environmental factors, and therefore ideal fits to answer the current research questions. FTA provided the structure of the interview and research programme as a whole, beginning the interview with the overview of an ‘event’ and its structure - in this case an overview of a regional safety challenge’s impact on a key farming population. The interview proceeded following FTA’s causal and exploratory logic in a three-part discussion on the causes, consequences, and then potential solutions to this issue. However, instead of exploring each ‘branch’ of a fault tree, this discussion was designed to investigate how the chosen phenomena were shaped by actors at levels of the SEM (individual, interpersonal, organisational, cultural, and policy/governance). We developed the base focus group script (see Annex 3) to be semi-structured and conversational (Kallio et al., 2016) to allow for straightforward translation, and easy adaptation to one-on-one data collection if needed across CoPs. This script provides the basic order of the conversation, allowing for participants to offer their own expertise while the discussion leader prompts participants with follow-up questions to explore a topic with more depth or bring up previously unmentioned dimensions (e.g. levels of the SEM). Throughout development, the script was collectively reviewed by the research team, who applied their collective expertise in a wide variety of social science and OSH disciplines as applied to agriculture. This cooperative development also included consultations with the wider ‘periodic’ Irish CoP which was fundamental in codifying the third part of the discussion ‘potential solutions’ to help participants tie both causes and consequences to meaningful outcomes and future actions.

3.3. Analytical Approach

This study involved two stages of analysis. The first one, performed by CoPs on regional data to the specifications outlined above, and the second consisting of the analysis presented in this report which

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represents a cross-national synthesis of secondary data reported by CoP partners in their Technical Note (TN) 9. This analysis followed a similar process that was provided for CoPs informed by RTA (Braun & Clarke, 2021): using the analytical team's expertise and subjective standpoints to interpret data through the lens of the SEM. Similarly, as an analysis of secondary data our methodology includes some of the assumptions of meta-syntheses (Walsh & Down, 2005). Specifically, the goal was not to identify the exact experiences of the participants across these CoP studies but to identify the common patterns across the studies themselves. Therefore, as each TN already represented an in-depth and multi-level report of primary data, we took an explicitly top-down and theoretically informed (primarily using Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) to identify temporal and causal links and SEM to identify interrelationships between levels) approach to the coding, organisation, and interpretation of this secondary data. This analysis involved preliminarily coding the information across TNs by causes, consequences, and solutions at multiple levels of the SEM and multiple categories of Causes, Consequences, and Solutions reflecting the complexity of multiple concepts.

This coding process was followed by more comprehensive coding and analysis of the emergent concepts. The aim of this cross-national analysis is not only to summarise the TNs, but also to explain the interrelationship between factors, the flow of causality, across socioecological levels and regions to identify the most important causes and consequences of these varied farm safety challenges on multiple key populations of farmers. A fundamental assumption of SEM is that individual experiences are contextualised and shaped by other levels, such as the family, and culture (Bronfenbrenner, 2000). Our analytical goal was to identify the causal logic, or the patterns to how causes from each SEM level shaped safety challenges in question (e.g. machinery accidents) and how consequences of these challenges impact each level in turn. While these causal logics could take multiple forms, the most expected causal logic would be a feedback loops between an individual and another level based on the established farm safety literature, the assumptions of the SEM, and the design of these focus groups. For example, in Ireland, off-farm employment (organisational level) increases the risk of farm accidents (individual level) and consequentially, can necessitate a reorganisation of farm management strategies (organisational level) (McNamara et al., 2021). This 'feedback loop' is not the only possible pattern, with one-way (higher level cause and lower-level consequence or the reverse), cascading (a series of causes/consequences proceeding across levels), or combinations of patterns possible. Finally, based on our primary findings, we incorporated further theoretical constructs, primarily Time Poverty (Vickery, 1977; Giurge et al., 2020), which we review in section 4.2.

The final analysis identified (1) an overarching causal logic that describes the directions of causes and consequences across the dataset, (2) a primary theme represented across nearly all other themes as an exacerbating factor and (3) four other important themes that illustrate how either the causal logic or primary theme play out across different domains.

3.4 Limitations and Reflexivity

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting findings and applying recommendations. Primarily that the data presented here is the result of several subsequent subjective analyses. This diversity of experiences and expertise is not a shortcoming, but an important constraint on how our findings should be understood: as the product of subsequent analyses by experts of diverse backgrounds and skills. While this process resulted in a relatively consistent dataset and clear findings reported from each CoP, it also necessitated many interpretive and analytical choices at both the national and cross-national level.

The first level of subjective analysis involves participants own insights, as this study collected data on **knowledge about**, rather than **personal experiences of**, farm safety challenges. the original Survivor Stories methodology would have centred on farmers' first-hand accounts of injury and recovery. However, the current research draws instead on expert knowledge from stakeholders and farmers about a range of challenges to farmers' health and safety. While the current approach was adopted for sound ethical reasons, it necessarily filters farmers' experiences through the perspectives of experts who may have no personal

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experience of these safety challenges (such as professionals who work with farming communities or other farmers themselves). However, instead of personal experience, these experts bring valuable systematic knowledge of many cases, but their accounts are interpretive rather than experiential. Future research that safely centres farmer voices—perhaps through anonymous written accounts or peer-led discussions—would complement this analysis.

At the second level of subjective analysis, CoP partners who collected and analysed data came from diverse professional backgrounds—including agricultural extension, social insurance, research institutes, and NGOs—and varied in their prior experience with qualitative research methods. Therefore, their interpretive and analytical choices were informed by their own subjective experience and relevant expertise. This was addressed through development of detailed guidance materials (Annex 1), an online Clinic to discuss methodology, and ongoing support throughout data collection and analysis. While this approach successfully produced coherent Technical Notes across all partners, some variation in analytical depth and approach remains visible across the dataset.

The third level of subjective analysis lies in our synthesis of secondary data. CoP partners produced Technical Notes analysing their primary data; the cross-national analysis reported here examined these Technical Notes rather than original transcripts. This layered approach enabled coordination across languages and contexts but means that some nuance present in primary data may not have carried through to the final synthesis. We addressed this through iterative consultation between the lead author and CoP partners during Technical Note development. This involved support and discussion from the beginning stages of schedule design and data collection through to the analysis, writing, and revision stages. Throughout this process, the lead author and CoP partners worked to prioritise clarity and communicability of themes from primary analysis.

Additionally, the sample size of 65 participants across 11 countries, while appropriate for qualitative research identifying transferable insights, limits the depth of analysis possible within any single national context. Some CoPs conducted rich focus group discussions with multiple participants, while others had smaller samples of in-depth interviews. This variation reflects the pragmatic realities of coordinating multi-country qualitative research within project timelines and partner capacity. Therefore, these results should not be interpreted as statistically representative of farmers' safety challenges. Indeed, CoP partners' selection of focus group/interview topics from their Needs Register means that this data does not represent a comprehensive map of European farm safety concerns. Challenges that fall outside national priorities, or that affect populations less visible to CoP networks, may be underrepresented. Rather, we identified important shared patterns across diverse contexts that point toward systemic features of European agricultural safety worth further investigation.

Finally, the Time Poverty framework introduced in section 4.2 represents an analytical interpretation that we identified from patterns *across* the dataset rather than a theme *explicitly* articulated by participants. While we believe this framework usefully synthesises findings about temporal pressures, workload, and systemic resource allocation, it involves a level of theoretical inference that extends beyond direct participant accounts. We offer it as a lens for understanding the data and a hypothesis for future research rather than a definitive conclusion.

Despite these limitations, the consistency of certain findings across diverse national contexts, safety challenges, and farming populations suggests that the patterns identified—particularly the hierarchical flow of causes from policy to individual levels, and the centrality of time as an exchanged resource—warrant serious consideration by policymakers and practitioners working to improve farm safety across the EU.

4. Results

This section presents the findings from cross-national synthesis of qualitative data collected across 11 Communities of Practice. We first present the overarching hierarchical logic identified across all countries (Section 4.1), then examine time poverty as the central mechanism through which this hierarchy operates (Section 4.2). Subsequent sections explore how this hierarchical logic manifests in specific domains: regulatory culture (4.3), cross-stakeholder collaboration (4.4), technology (4.5), and gender and family (4.6).

4.1. Hierarchical Causal Logic

This analysis identified a primary overarching logic linking high-level policy and governance decisions with the wellbeing and safety of farmers through a downward cascade of causes. We also identified two complementary patterns describing how consequences flow: upwards through socioecological levels and through intensification within levels. This section presents each pattern in turn, before briefly situating these findings within existing research.

4.1.1 Primary Logic: Downward Cascade

Across all 11 regional analyses and contrary to our expected findings, we identified a broad disconnect between the socioecological level where causal factors originate and where consequences are experienced. Causes of safety issues cascade downwards from policy and governance decisions, ultimately shaping the working conditions and therefore health and safety of farmers, farmworkers, and families. Causes are heavily concentrated at policy and organisational levels: inadequate infrastructure, poor regulatory enforcement, systemic financial pressures, restrictive immigration regimes, and insufficient institutional support. Yet consequences fall overwhelmingly on individual farmers and workers, and their immediate families: physical injuries, psychological suffering, financial struggles, social isolation, and reduced access to important services.

While this disconnect is most evident between policy-level causes and individual-level consequences, these causes cascade through intermediary socioecological levels. Primarily, decisions and actions at higher levels increase precarity and apply pressure to actors and decisions made at lower levels. In general, policy-level pressures (e.g. low producer prices, inadequate subsidies) force organisational-level resource-cutting of time and money (e.g. understaffing, deferring maintenance) which ultimately result in individual and interpersonal harm (farm injuries, chronic stress, exploitation).

Three country examples illustrate this pattern:

Spain: Policy-level treatment of immigrants and immigration creates the context for exploitation of immigrant labour by agricultural corporations. This exploitation manifests as inadequate working and living conditions, such as substandard housing. These conditions then lead to health crises and social (and spatial) exclusion experienced by migrants.

Lithuania and Slovenia: Financial and market pressures push many farmers into dual employment. This constant workload creates time scarcity and necessitates overworking. These harmful patterns of work then manifest in farming family strain, deteriorating mental health, and substance use.

Romania: Financial constraints on farms lead to high turnover rates as farmworkers seek better or more stable pay elsewhere. This creates a challenging context for training employees, resulting in many workers receiving insufficient training, and facing increased accident risks, and/or facing heavy time pressures and increased burnout risk.

Together, these and other Technical Notes represent safety in the agricultural sector as largely organised around power and agency, where decisions and resource allocation (including capital, time, and labour) at higher levels shape the realistic constraints faced by more systemically disempowered actors at lower

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levels. While farm safety challenges may be directly caused by individual behaviours, work-organisational issues, or lack of awareness, they are ultimately not just contextualised by (as the SEM framework establishes) but in our analysis *caused* by much broader structural factors. This primarily one-way causal flow describes the European agricultural system as a hierarchy with farmers and other producers occupying the lowest tier, facing the repercussions of decisions made across other levels.

4.1.2 Secondary Logics: Upwards and Intensifying Cascades

While the primary pattern demonstrates a downward cascade from policy decisions toward individual occupational safety and health issues, this logic primarily concerns chains of *causes* that lead to specific safety concerns. However, *consequences* follow different though complementary patterns. These consequential logics are not entirely separated from the downward causal cascade. Rather, they illustrate how consequences are not felt only by individuals suffering them but ripple outwards to affect others and can amplify existing conditions. Specifically, we identified two patterns: consequences flowing **upwards** through socioecological levels and **intensification** within levels.

Upward Flow of Consequences

When consequences flow upwards, they usually proceed from the individual to the organisational level. Individual injuries and illnesses may generate household labour crises; these accumulated household impacts can strain community resources and service capacity; and organisational-level consequences affect policy responses and resource allocation. This upward flow is particularly evident in how individual farmer burnout and injury affect organisational viability.

Romania documented that workers leaving farm businesses because of heavy workloads or financial pressures can create challenging contexts for farming organisations and farm owners to train new workers. High turnover also amplifies owners' time and financial strain, resulting in reduced capacity to train new staff, making workplaces less safe, which then further destabilises farm operations. Similarly, Spain's data showed how individual migrant worker health crises and exploitation contribute to community-level spatial exclusion and ultimately threaten the agricultural sector's labour supply and reputation, demonstrating how consequences at lower levels aggregate to create higher-level systemic challenges.

Intensification Within Levels

Consequences also demonstrate intensification within the same socioecological level where they occur, creating self-reinforcing cycles. At the individual level, mental health deterioration from time poverty and stress reduces farmers' capacity to manage workloads effectively, leading to further time scarcity and additional stress—documented across Lithuania, Slovenia, and Ireland. The Irish data specifically illustrated this through cycles where older farmers' inability to step back from demanding physical work (due to identity, succession delays, or labour shortages) leads to injuries that force operational changes, yet these adaptations often involve continued exposure to risk because the underlying labour shortage remains unresolved.

At the interpersonal level, several countries documented how family labour redistribution following an injury increases secondary injury risk for other household members, further jeopardising labour distribution, and amplifying risk.

4.1.3 Situating These Findings

The hierarchical patterns identified in this analysis—where policy and market-level decisions cascade through organisational structures to shape individual farmers' safety outcomes and where consequences intensify this effect—align with and extend existing research on farm stress, labour dynamics, and occupational health.

Well-established literature documents how structural and policy factors shape farmer wellbeing. The "cost-price squeeze"—where input costs rise while producer prices stagnate or decline—has been identified as

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a fundamental driver of farm stress across European and international contexts (Lobley et al., 2004; Gregoire, 2002). Farmers absorb these systemic pressures through labour intensification: extending working hours, deferring maintenance, and reducing hired labour to maintain viability (Johnsen, 2004). Time pressure and rushing have been consistently identified as proximal causes of farm accidents (Sprince et al., 2002), while systematic reviews identify workload, fatigue, and inadequate rest as mediating pathways between economic stress and accident occurrence (Caffaro et al., 2018).

The specific role of time as a constrained resource in farming contexts has received growing attention. Recent Irish research demonstrates substantial variation in labour efficiency, with the most efficient dairy farmers working 51 hours per week during peak season compared with 70 hours for the least efficient—despite managing similar herd sizes (Hogan et al., 2022a). Critically, improved labour efficiency correlates with better farmer wellbeing and profitability, suggesting that time poverty carries both human and economic costs (Hogan et al., 2023). Our findings should be understood not as novel claims, but as qualitative confirmation of dynamics that quantitative and theoretical work has identified. The contribution of the current analysis lies in demonstrating these patterns empirically across 11 diverse European contexts and applying the Socioecological Model to assess causal pathways.

The centrality of time as a resource exchanged between socioecological levels—identified consistently across our data—warrants dedicated examination. Section 4.2 therefore introduces Time Poverty as an integrative framework that connects structural pressures to embodied safety outcomes

4.2. Time Poverty

While this hierarchical logic plays out across these themes, time was a characteristic of nearly every causal chain. In this way, time operates as both a cause, consequence, and solution; in this dataset it is the resource exchanged between SEM levels that is most meaningfully connected to farm safety. This surprising (to us) result necessitates a theoretical framework (to synthesise with the SEM) that can conceptualise time as not just the documentation of changes over time, but as a resource used within a system as money and other forms of capital are.

We identified Time Poverty (Vickery, 1977; Giurge et al., 2020) as the most appropriate framework to analyse this finding of time as a resource. Time poverty is a theory developed to examine how shortages of money are not the only stressors placed on household, and that shortages of time can similarly impact household members' wellbeing (Vickery, 1977). Time poverty effectively describes time (like and related to money/capital) as a driver of agency and power. A person in poverty's agency, and therefore their ability to support their health and wellbeing, is constrained by their lack of income. Similarly, a person who is in time poverty's agency, and again their ability to support their health and wellbeing, is limited by the time resources that they have. Time poverty is therefore a useful lens to identifying how other actors across the agricultural system (from governing bodies to individuals) have or lack access to time (Giurge et al., 2020). Indeed, though it is rarely included in SEM analyses of agriculture (see Lee et al., 2017), the 'chronosphere' was a fundamental component of Bronfenbrenner's original conception of the SEM; the highest level of the model describing both how individuals' engagement with levels of the SEM changes as they develop and how the systems embedded in each also change (1979). Similarly, while Marx identified time as fundamentally important in organising labour (Marx, 1867) it remains a critically under recognised dimension of poverty across many contexts (Giurge et al., 2020). Time poverty is a novel approach to examining farmers' health and wellbeing (Scheyett et al., 2025), and a completely novel (as of writing) lens to examining farmers' safety. While busyness is increasingly a status symbol for many professions (see Keinan et al., 2019), it is particularly relevant for farmers who see working hard and working constantly as a fundamental part of their occupational identity (Firnhaber et al., 2024) and could be particularly susceptible to time poverty even when managing productive farms. Time poverty allows us to conceptualise the inverse of this – not how hard farmers are working but how much time they have agency over that they could devote to actions which support their health and wellbeing. Therefore, time poverty

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provides a way for the current analysis to examine how time is spent across SEM levels in this dataset and identify if these systems are creating time or eliminating time, and for whom.

Effectively, our analysis identified time poverty as a subtle, but central, exacerbating root causal factor of farmers' OSH challenges in this dataset due to its presence across SEM levels, its importance as a precedent to many serious farm health and safety challenges (e.g. machinery accidents, mental illness, chronic stress), and its utility as an analytical lens to highlight power differentials across the dataset. As a causal factor, rushing and time pressure appear in nearly every report as primary accident factors; driven by seasonal demands, legislative demands, weather dependencies, financial pressures, and understaffing. The consequences of these and other causes are largely *amplifications* of these time-constraints. For example, farm accidents and injuries create disruptions to the temporal organisation of work and labour on farms: lost work time, pressure on other employees, delayed harvests, extended recovery periods, and in some cases shortened working lives. In this example, time poverty *is not* the most dangerous causal factor; indeed, where we identify this phenomenon in the dataset, it is not the main cause of OHS issues. Rather it is an important exacerbating factor across SEM levels.

Our findings of a downward cascade of time poverty that is both systemic and often subtle matches a common bioecological phenomenon in structure: Biomagnification (see Gray, 2002). Essentially, some pollutants (such as mercury) in an ecosystem (such as the ocean) collect in the bodies of organisms in that ecosystem faster than they can be eliminated. However, this process continues and magnifies at each level of the food chain, resulting in a higher concentration of pollutants at each stage. In many cases, these pollutants are at too low levels of concentration to harm organisms until they reach the top of the food chains, in some cases humans (U.N., 2021). We identified a similar process in this dataset, where the time shortages or production pressures may be far from the minds of policymakers and other stakeholders, but they magnify and further constrain decisions farther down the SEM levels until they manifest as farmers' experiences of time poverty. For example, Ireland's analysis describes how these higher-level gaps in policy or governance can specifically endanger older farmers' OHS by presenting them with a range of hard choices and a significant demand on their time, energy, and labour.

“Primarily, we identified that machinery accidents arise as older farmers put their own health and safety at risk by using their individual energy and wellbeing to bridge gaps at other socioecological levels; in governance, labour, machinery, profits, or expertise. In all cases, these cycles produced high-pressure time-shortages for older farmers working at unsustainable and unsafe paces and putting themselves at risk as a result. This resulting time pressure was captured in the contrast between a ‘busy farm’ (well managed, productive, well-staffed and well equipped) and a ‘busy farmer’ (rushing to complete jobs, under pressure, stressed and fatigued).”

As this extract illustrates, time poverty also exemplifies how the two consequential logics (upwards and intensification) interact with the central downwards cascade to form recursive patterns: consequences can regenerate the causal conditions that produced them. When injuries remove farmers from work, remaining household members must absorb additional labour while maintaining the same production schedules, intensifying the time scarcity that likely contributed to the initial injury. This pattern was also explicit in Finnish and Estonian data documenting how staff shortages and seasonal workload peaks lead to fatigue and rushing (causal cascade), which produce injuries (consequences), which then worsen staffing and increase workload pressure for remaining workers. This upwards flow of consequences therefore intensifies the conditions that led to the original causes. Similarly, financial strain as both a cause and consequence demonstrates this recursivity: policy-level economic pressures force organisational cost-cutting and understaffing (causal cascade), injuries generate medical costs and lost productivity (consequences), these financial impacts limit capacity for safety investments and potentially force further cost reductions. These cycles again intensifies original causes, perpetuating and worsening unsafe conditions. Therefore, both upwards and intensifying logics intensify the existing hierarchical organisation of the European agricultural system and further the time burdens experienced by farmers.

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Therefore, instead of the current European agricultural system creating a surplus of time for its participants, time is instead a resource *used* by this system, and time debt is one of the burdens handed down from the policy level through SEM levels into the hands of primary producers – farmers, workers, and families. While the intention of the system (e.g. through direct payments and other supports) is to support farmers *financial* security and national/European food security, through this analysis, we identified that this system also may exacerbate time poverty for those at the lowest level of this chain.

Fittingly, many solutions discussed across these 11 TNs involve addressing these temporal imbalances to create more time (and therefore alleviate time poverty) for agricultural producers to live, work, and rest. Individual level solutions include personal adaptations such as scheduling rest times and establishing succession plans to ensure both daily and end-of-career rest. Organisational-level solutions focus on fostering cooperation between farm businesses and other actors to improve efficiency as well as timing education, training, and service provision to be flexible and therefore accessible for farming communities. Policy, or macro-level solutions, such as implementing replacement worker services or schemes ensuring farmers and farmworkers have access to basic infrastructural necessities to live and work safely are arguably the most vital as this analysis identified the policy and governance-level as the beginning of this causal chain resulting in farm accidents and injuries.

4.3. Regulatory Culture

This second theme highlights power relationships within the agricultural system's hierarchy particularly well by illustrating which actors can structure the time of others. Multiple country reports described a tension between compliance-oriented and culture-based approaches to farm safety, with significant implications for policy effectiveness. First, we identified a negative perception of many current regulatory practices that exemplify the overarching logic of cascading time burdens. Participants from Slovakia, Romania, Finland, and Germany described occupational safety regulations as bureaucratic burdens – and wastes of time - disconnected from their actual safety needs. Germany's report focused extensively on this, identifying the complex challenges of implementing a (superficially) simple regulation for seat belt use in tractors; 83% of farmers regularly go without seatbelts, describing them as bothersome, uncomfortable, and unnecessary. Romania's participants similarly reported that administrative duties were almost as demanding as farming itself and identified that rules were sometimes impractical for daily operations. Finally, Finland's data described that even when farmers demonstrate strong safety awareness, they aren't always willing to adhere to safety regulations as they saw these as extra obligations. Slovakia's data describes how these administrative burdens can exacerbate farmers' time pressures particularly well.

“Agricultural small and medium enterprises (SMEs) face a high administrative burden due to the complex and extensive occupational safety and health (OSH) regulations, record-keeping requirements, and reporting obligations. These tasks often include maintaining detailed logs, performing mandatory equipment inspections, completing compliance forms, and documenting risk assessments. For small and medium-sized farms, OSH responsibilities are typically managed by an employee who handles OSH as a secondary task, or by the farmer themselves. This results in significant time investment, distraction from core farming operations. Farmers in agricultural SMEs often perceive that certain OSH regulations, procedures, or administrative requirements are unnecessary. While they generally understand the importance of safety, many rules are seen as disconnected from actual farm risks or too formalized, focusing more on documentation than practical safety. This perception can lead to minimal compliance, selective adherence, or even skipping certain administrative tasks, especially when they are time-consuming or costly.”

This theme offers strong support to the ongoing research on the costs of farmers' administrative work (Benni et al., 2020), and how valuable farmers' time is (Girvan & Mitchell, 2020). It is well-established that the paperwork, administrative burdens of farming, and necessity to adapt to changing regulation and guidelines, are a significant driver of farmers' stress (Parry et al., 2005; Firnhaber et al., 2024; Whitaker, 2024). However, this analysis highlights a temporal and pragmatic explanation. If farmers perceive regulatory requirements -

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especially in a compliance-based system - as yet another time burden, their reluctance to engage with safety regulations (and their non-compliance) can be understood as attempts to manage their workload. Effectively, farmers' time is in short supply as one of their most valuable resources, and they are allocating their time and labour to the aspects of their jobs most closely related to their day-to-day farming operations (Girvan & Mitchell, 2020). Regulation, education, and guidance designed to support farmers' OSH and prevent injuries can be harmful to farmers' wellbeing as well if it costs them significant time to engage with; even beneficial and supportive regulation can cause significant hardship when it fits poorly with farmers' needs (Whitaker, 2024). Therefore, safety regulation should be integrated, as much as possible, into farmers' daily work and address issues they see as the most important risks they face (see deliverable 3.3).

Farmers' opposition towards regulatory burdens create important barriers to implementing farm safety education and training (among other interventions). To address this, TNs emphasised that effectively advancing farm safety requires cultural transformation alongside regulatory reform. These discussions identified that approaches centred on practically understanding farmers' safety concerns, encouraging peer influence, and supporting adaptation to specific local and geographical contexts are all important approaches. The important unifying theme to these culture-based approaches is they are all designed to be embedded into farmers' existing patterns of labour, or as services provided for farmers and not additional clerical or other labour (however beneficial) that uses farmers' valuable time. Slovenia's work focused most closely on this and highlighted the importance of mutual identification between advisors and farmers for successful interventions. When advisors understand farmers' occupational concerns, farmers are more willing to trust and identify with advisors, and therefore conversations between farmers and advisors can normalise safety behaviours in ways that regulation cannot. Policy should therefore invest in cultural infrastructure (peer networks, demonstration farms, trusted advisors) alongside compliance mechanisms, ensuring that regulations are designed for relevance and usability rather than administrative oversight; well-intentioned safety regulation can add to root causes of farm accidents, like time-poverty. For example, solutions like Finland's QR-coded task-specific instructions, and Germany's comfort-focused seat belt redesigns exemplify ways to embed safety information and end-user-friendly engineering respectively into farmers' daily work and lives.

4.4 Cross-Stakeholder Collaboration

Nearly every country's results identified the consistent lack of coordination among stakeholders as a cause of safety challenges and an important characteristic of many different solutions. Spain noted that actors often work in isolation which can lead to regulatory gaps and a lack of important service provision. Lithuania identified insufficient leadership in organisations, and poor communications across unions which can lead to fractures and tension between different representative bodies. This fragmentation has different impacts in different regions, but it nearly always results in wasted time. Important problems fall through the cracks and are never addressed by safety stakeholders and governance systems, leaving farmers and families to address these directly. When problems are addressed, efforts can be duplicated at best (wasting institutional time and resources) or designed in contradiction to each other at worst (spending farmers' time and resources). The latter especially contributes to the second theme of regulation, leaving farmers to face contradictory demands from different agencies with competing mandates or policy objectives (Whitaker, 2024). This coordination failure is often structural, as national farm safety systems may lack formal mechanisms to align their efforts (Deliverable 1.6). Even more, imbalances of power between OSH partnerships can cause fractures of trust and collaboration (Jones & Barry, 2018). Romania provided a detailed description of how addressing a lack of coordination between farmers and multiple stakeholders, and between stakeholders themselves, could provide skills and training for farmers need to balance costs, labour, time, and safety on the farm. In this way, improving stakeholder communication can improve the governance or education system for farmers and by doing so support their daily health and safety.

“Organizational level solutions focussed on educational and training solutions. As such, at work, it was suggested to coordinate veterinary and sanitary trainings organised by state-owned veterinary offices,

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implementation, and support of continuous education programmes for employees. Another solution, to strengthen and to develop new collaborations between educational institutions and private farmers, for the students to take part in practical programmes (during agricultural season), to better understand farm work and farm environment. In terms of policy measures, most of the identified solutions, bring forward the need to focus on a reorganization of labour inspectorates' method of operation. In this direction, the participants have suggested the implementation of regular sessions of OHS trainings and advising sessions organised by the labour inspectorate, simplification of the language used in laws and trainings [and] employing new channels of communication for updates and particular topics. A solution mentioned on multiple instances was the need to coordinate the school curriculum and agricultural labour' needs. This includes dedicated technical schools and training, as well as improvements of the educational level of farm employees.”

Across the dataset, solutions emphasised the need for formalised, ongoing coordination structures rather than ad-hoc cooperation. For example, Spain proposed establishing permanent multi-actor working groups that convene before each agricultural season, bringing together producers, workers, NGOs, and authorities to proactively plan housing solutions and contingency measures. This structure is similar to Ireland's Farm Safety Partnership, which brings together governmental, OSH and other stakeholders to coordinate actions across organisations. However, Ireland also identified a critical gap in manufacturer engagement: unlike construction and mining sectors, agricultural equipment is delivered with minimal or no training, and manufacturers must be integrated into safety governance systems. Lithuania emphasised that strengthening leadership and communication skills among farmer associations may help strengthen capacity to effectively participate in multi-stakeholder dialogues. These recommendations point towards two key mechanisms: regularly convening multi-actor partnerships between organisations and dedicated and ongoing resources to sustain joint efforts. Most simply, multi-level coordination is essential to addressing time poverty for producers. Therefore, allocating resources to higher level coordination is one of the most straightforward mechanisms we identified to alleviating time poverty in farmers. This has the potential to address competing regulation and regulatory gaps, as well as ensure service provision is designed and conducted in culturally appropriate and needs-based ways.

4.5 Technology: Solution and Stressor

Technology was an important component to many causes and solutions to farm safety challenges and exemplifies the importance of understanding efficiency as not just bound by questions of time, but power. Contrary to persistent narratives around the importance of increasing digitisation and mechanisation in agriculture (Jasonoff, 2015; Cardona et al., 2025) these TNs describe a complex relationship between technology. On one hand, technology holds a promising solution to numerous safety challenges, notably the potential to save farmers' time in engaging with safety information. On the other hand, the increasing digitisation and reliance on technological solutions without proper support could harm farmers and place even more time pressures (upskilling, additional record keeping, even tighter timetables) on the already time-poor. For example, the Slovak CoP recommended user-friendly digital tools could streamline record-keeping, which could reduce time spent dealing with the paperwork and lighten other regulatory burdens. Yet, multiple countries documented that constant digital connectivity could extend vigilance beyond working hours, e.g. with farmers monitoring barns via their smartphones in ways that undermine rest and recovery. The complex relationship between digitisation and farming is most clear in the data from Slovenia where digital connectivity exacerbates a cycle of overwork, and necessary steps to interrupt this cycle involve reestablishing healthy rhythms of rest and recovery.

“Aside from working hours, the constant sense of responsibility for animals, plants, machinery, and regulatory compliance, exacerbated by digital surveillance, undermines recovery time. Some farmers reported feeling judged as 'incompetent' workers, leading to early return from sick leave and increased stress. Others reported friction with relatives living with them and less time and energy for children, which was replaced by more screen time and accompanied by feelings of guilt. At the farm level, the

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main consequence was a reduced ability to work: stress and burnout led to periods of incapacity or reduced productivity, and time off from off-farm activities rarely provided relief from farming duties: *“Let's say, if a person is employed in a company and has too many tasks, they sometimes burn out because they can't cope, and I think the same thing happens to farmers: we have a lot of things to do, a lot of responsibilities, and then, when it all piles up, a person can't cope anymore and problems arise.* At the organisational level (farm), the solution is to reorganise work to protect recovery and identify early warning signs to prevent sickness presenteeism: educating farmers about burnout, modelling rest periods within farming routines and extending the presence of advisors and extension services on farms who are familiar with machinery, seasonal rhythms, and constraints.”

In this way, technology use on farms mirrors global work-culture shifts across other industries (Giurge et al., 2020). Effectively, digitalisation and technological advancement in agriculture can isolate farmers from risky working environments and can at the same time exacerbate challenges farmers are already dealing with; in Romania, farmers with low digital literacy benefit very little and are isolated even further, by digital solutions. We argue that in this dataset, technological advancement like digitisation is not inherently a solution, but rather reinforces and highlights existing power inequalities within the agricultural system (Hackfort, 2021). Through the lens of time poverty, we identified who the proposed solution is creating efficiency for (who it is giving more time to) and who must do the work of implementing and maintaining it (who it is taking time from) are key delineating points between whether technology hurts or harms farmers' OSH. To prevent technological solutions from further disadvantaging struggling farmers, they must be implemented in ways which redistribute time to farmers and other agricultural workers. An excellent example of redistributing time is Slovenia's recommendation for embedding a "right to disconnect" in farm safety culture and guidance. This has implications on technological solutions as well. For example, Germany and Estonia suggest technological improvements such as improving tractor cab and milking parlour ergonomics respectively. If these improvements are only implemented as guidelines provided for farmers to then implement using their own resources (including time), then these implementations are unlikely to work even if farmers are motivated to do them. If, however, the labour to perform these technical upgrades is provided by social insurance or governance authorities, or these improvements are implemented in the design of products (as suggested by Ireland), then they stand to improve farmers' safety without contributing to their existing burdens.

4.6 Gender and Family

Finally, Gender and Family together were key issues in multiple TNs and serve as a case example for how power hierarchies in European agricultural system can concentrate health and safety challenges in certain groups. We identified that women and farming family members of any gender are examples of groups that, when lacking access to power in their local setting, are disproportionately affected by inequalities in labour and work allocation. For example, in Estonia's dairy industry, women represent 63% of accidents despite comprising only 23-25% of the workforce. This overrepresentation stems from gender-segregated task allocation in this country's intensive Dairying industry, with women concentrated in repetitive, time consuming, direct-contact roles such as milking and animal care that carry the highest injury rates. Similarly, Lithuania identified how patriarchal succession practices can place economic pressure on farming children of any gender, who often serve as the family's "safety guarantee" (guaranteed labour) while bearing the additional burden of domestic labour, supporting older generations, and caring for their own families. Poland provided a particularly powerful account of how time-pressures and workload allocation decisions can impact families, particularly endangering children on farms. This case exemplifies how time-poverty can have very real impacts on farmers and their families.

“routine, rush, and underestimation of risks remain some of the most significant factors contributing to unsafe behaviour in agriculture. Farmers often operate under time pressure, with heavy workloads and repetitive tasks, which can lead to neglecting safety procedures and reacting incorrectly in dangerous situations. [] Insufficient supervision of children during periods of intensive farm work often

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leads to dangerous situations and accidents. When adults, sometimes showing little awareness of the dangers to children, are occupied with demanding agricultural tasks, children may be left unattended and exposed to various hazards, such as machinery, animals, or unsafe areas on the farm. These individual, interpersonal and organisational reasons may result in accidents causing serious injuries and long-term consequences for both children and their families. To prevent such incidents, it is important to undertake in the local community activities aimed [at] organising childcare facilities for rural children during the summer holidays and other times of increased fieldwork, ensuring they are in a safe and engaging environment while their parents work”

These examples are evidence of a longstanding - though often shifting and sometimes harmonious - pattern of unequal labour practices in European agriculture (Contzen & Forney, 2017). While arrangement may be perceived as pragmatic to the individuals making these work allocation decisions (e.g. the farmworker who applied for the position in Estonia, Romania, or Spain is a woman) they result in systematic inequalities across the industry (Contzen & Forney, 2017). In addition to these organisational inequalities, women particularly face risks of direct interpersonal abuse. Indeed, several TNs identified the ongoing link between financial issues and women’s experiences of domestic (and in the case of farming families, also workplace) violence (Wendt & Hornosty, 2014). Specifically, Spain documented cases of sexual harassment and coercion by supervisors that women (specifically migrant) workers are afraid to report as this might jeopardise their ability to source seasonal contracts and exclude them from future employment opportunities.

Despite this evidence of risks to women and farming family members, discussions across these TNs rarely identified solutions to explicitly address these dimensions. This can be interpreted in two ways. First, these cases are not evidence that every woman in agriculture suffers, or that every farming family faces heightened risk, or even that women or family members are a vulnerable population in general. Rather, these cases highlight power inequalities within the agricultural system which allow for these threats to women’s and families’ OSH to occur. Effectively, addressing root causes will improve not only women farmers’ occupational health but the health of any workers who face systemic inequalities. Poland’s proposed solution of childcare is an excellent example, as strengthening access to childcare helps keep children out of harm’s way on the farm, alleviates burdens on farming women and other caregivers, and creates more time for the family (Becot et al., 2022). Similarly, Spain’s recommendation - supporting and empowering workers against retaliation – would benefit workers belonging to multiple groups and facing different challenges. However, there is also a need for further gender-based solutions. Estonia’s gender-centric analysis provided an exemplary recommendation of ensuring that training and equipment (e.g. milking parlours) are gender-sensitive and designed for the roles that women actually perform. However, these discussions did not identify solutions specifically for the gendered distribution of labour, or the inordinate time poverty that women farmers sometimes contend with. This could reflect the ongoing lack of protections for women, or mechanisms to identify specific inequalities faced by women, in the EU agricultural system (Shortall & Vangelis, 2022). Effective interventions must therefore recognise how cultural and institutional inequalities can shape task allocation patterns and ultimately expose women and other workers to differential hazards. Treating women solely as independent workers, wage owners, and managers can be framed as empowering, but can also obscure any exploitation (low wage, time consuming, or dangerous work) in these roles and the domestic labour women may be obligated to do (Contzen & Forney, 2017; Dean et al., 2022; Mackintosh, 2023). As with other themes across this dataset, these findings indicate that without explicit attention to systematic power imbalances, safety interventions may inadvertently harm the populations most vulnerable to those workplace risks.

5. Findings

In line with key objectives set for the SafeHabitus project, we conducted research among 11 CoPs as part of Work Package 3 to identify the root causes and consequences of farm safety challenges among key groups of farmers. This was done in support of the development of policy options that enhance policy and governance frameworks leading to improved working conditions in agriculture. In completing this work, this

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report contributes key 'Expected Outcomes' that were established by the EU when the call for research proposals on the topic of farm safety and farmer / worker health was published in 2022. In particular, the analysis and recommendations support Outcome 1, *to enhance understanding and awareness by policy makers, farmers' organisations, trade unions, and health authorities on the implications of their work on the future of the sector*, and Outcome 4, *to improve health, safety, and labour conditions in farming thanks to better performing European and national policy and legal frameworks*. Acting on the recommendations set out below will provide policy stakeholders and policy makers at both EU and national levels with key conceptual frameworks and implementation goals required to develop strategies and targeted initiatives that improve working conditions, address root causes of OSH risks, and enhance the wellbeing, safety, and working conditions of farmers, farmworkers, families and any who live or work on European farms.

5.1 Policy and Practice Recommendations

The findings presented in Section 4 point toward specific policy reforms and practice changes that can address the hierarchical causation and systemic time poverty affecting European farmers' health and safety. Perhaps most significant for policy development, the analysis reveals temporal asymmetries between causes and consequences. While specific causal factors may be traced to discrete policy decisions or organisational practices that can be changed, consequences unfold across extended timescales and accumulate in ways that may be hard to detect yet be dramatically destabilising. The generational renewal crisis described across multiple countries exemplifies this: immediate causal factors (time pressure, inadequate pay, dangerous conditions) produce immediate consequences (injuries, stress), but these accumulate over years to create consequences that impact the entire sector across multiple levels (declining sector attractiveness, aging workforce, succession failures) that fundamentally reshape the agricultural labour system. This temporal dimension means that interventions addressing only immediate causal factors may not prevent long-term consequences, while consequences visible today may reflect causal conditions from years or decades past. To accommodate this, the recommendations below are organised according to their implementation pathway and timeline, recognising that different policy mechanisms operate on different cycles and through different governance structures.

We distinguish between:

- **Tier 1 recommendations** that can be implemented within the current CAP programming period (2023-2027) through Member State Strategic Plan amendments or existing governance mechanisms
- **Tier 2 recommendations** that align with specific elements of the proposed Post-2027 CAP framework (2028-2034) and should be considered during the current legislative negotiation process
- **Tier 3 vision elements** that require longer-term systemic change beyond the current policy cycle

This tiered approach reflects the reality that meaningful improvement in farm safety requires action at multiple levels and timescales. Some improvements can begin immediately; others require the policy windows that CAP reform provides; still others point toward a fundamentally different relationship between agricultural policy and farmer wellbeing.

5.2 Tier 1: Immediate Opportunities (2023-2027)

These recommendations can be implemented within existing frameworks without new legislation.

5.2.1 Gender-Disaggregated Safety Data Collection

Finding addressed: Finding 6 (Gender inequalities)

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Recommendation: Eurostat and national statistical offices should systematically collect and report farm injury and occupational health data disaggregated by gender, employment status, and farm type.

Implementation pathway: This is an administrative and methodological change that does not require new legislation. It can be implemented through:

- Revision of data collection protocols under existing Eurostat frameworks
- Guidance to Member States on reporting requirements
- Integration with existing Farm Structure Survey methodologies

Responsible bodies: Eurostat, national statistical agencies, DG AGRI

Reference: This aligns with the broader EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 commitment to improve gender-disaggregated data collection across policy domains.

5.2.2 Farm Safety Communities of Practice

Finding addressed: Finding 4 (Cross-stakeholder collaboration)

Recommendation: Member States should utilise existing LEADER funding and European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI) mechanisms to establish Farm Safety Communities of Practice modelled on the Irish Farm Safety Partnership.

Implementation pathway:

- LEADER Local Action Groups can include farm safety as a priority theme within existing Local Development Strategies
- EIP-AGRI Operational Groups can be established to address specific safety challenges identified in this research
- No Strategic Plan amendment required where these activities fall within existing intervention scope

Responsible bodies: Member State managing authorities, LEADER Local Action Groups, national rural networks

Policy reference:

- Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Article 77 (LEADER/community-led local development)
- Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Article 77(1)(a) specifically enables cooperation including "pilot projects"
- EIP-AGRI framework under Article 127 of Regulation (EU) 2021/2115

Note: The Irish Farm Safety Partnership provides a documented implementation model. The SafeHabitus CoP structure itself demonstrates the feasibility of cross-stakeholder collaboration on farm safety.

5.2.3 Integration of Time-Use Awareness in Farm Advisory Services

Finding addressed: Finding 2 (Time Poverty)

Recommendation: Farm Advisory Services (FAS) should incorporate time-use assessment and labour efficiency guidance as a standard component of advisory support, drawing on research demonstrating the connection between working hours, safety outcomes, and profitability.

Implementation pathway:

- Member States have flexibility to define FAS content within their Strategic Plans

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- This can be implemented as guidance to advisory bodies without Strategic Plan amendment
- Training materials can draw on existing research (e.g., Teagasc labour efficiency research, Hogan et al. 2022)

Responsible bodies: National FAS providers, Member State ministries, agricultural training bodies

Policy reference:

- Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Article 15 (Farm advisory services)
- Article 15(4)(a) requires FAS to cover "economic, environmental and social dimensions"

5.3 Tier 2: Post-2027 CAP Integration (2028-2034)

These recommendations align with specific elements of the proposed Post-2027 CAP framework and should be considered during the current legislative negotiation process between the European Parliament and Council.

5.3.1 Time Poverty Impact Assessment in CAP Design

Finding addressed: Finding 1 (Hierarchical causal logic); Finding 2 (Time Poverty)

Recommendation: The Commission and Member States should assess the time burden implications of new CAP measures during the design phase, ensuring that administrative requirements do not inadvertently exacerbate time poverty and associated safety risks for farmers.

Rationale: Our findings demonstrate that policy burdens cascade through the agricultural system, ultimately manifesting as time pressure at farm level. The Post-2027 CAP's emphasis on simplification provides an opportunity to institutionalise consideration of temporal impacts.

Implementation pathway:

- Integration into the Commission's CAP recommendations to Member States during National Plan preparation
- Development of assessment criteria as part of the Plan approval process
- This aligns with the broader simplification objective of the Post-2027 proposals

Policy reference:

- COM(2025) 565 (European Fund Regulation) – The Post-2027 CAP framework emphasises simplification and reducing administrative burden. The Commission's July 2025 proposal states that measures should deliver "simpler to manage for national administrations" outcomes.
- Article references for specific objectives and assessment requirements

Responsible bodies: DG AGRI, Member State ministries

5.3.2 Farm Stewardship and Working Conditions

Finding addressed: Finding 1 (Hierarchical causal logic); Finding 3 (Regulatory culture)

Recommendation: The design of protective practices under the new Farm Stewardship system should consider implementation feasibility for farm operators, avoiding requirements that create perverse incentives toward rushed or unsafe work practices.

Context and limitations: The proposed Farm Stewardship system (replacing current conditionality) focuses on environmental standards, animal welfare, and social rights compliance. Social conditionality

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provisions address employment law compliance for workers, including migrant and seasonal workers – this is important but does not directly address the working conditions of self-employed farmers themselves.

We recommend that:

- Protective practice design should include assessment of labour time requirements
- Member States should be encouraged to use flexibility provisions to adapt requirements to farm scale and type
- Implementation timelines should allow adequate adjustment periods

Policy reference:

- Proposed CAP Regulation, Article 3 (Farm Stewardship system) [VERIFY exact Article number]
- Social conditionality provisions in Annex – noting these apply to employer obligations, not self-employed farmers' own working time
- The Commission's Q&A (23 July 2025) states: "Farmers receiving CAP payments will have to respect standards on environment, animal welfare, and social rights. However, smaller and organic farms will face fewer obligations."

Important clarification: Social conditionality addresses compliance with employment law for hired workers. It does not regulate self-employed farmers' own working hours or conditions. Recommendations regarding farmers' own time use must work through other mechanisms (advisory services, investment support, knowledge transfer).

5.3.3 Investment Support for Time-Saving Infrastructure and Technology

Finding addressed: Finding 2 (Time Poverty); Finding 5 (Technology)

Recommendation: Member States should prioritise investment support for infrastructure and technologies that demonstrably reduce working time and improve labour efficiency, with particular attention to small and medium farms where time poverty is most acute.

Rationale: Research demonstrates substantial variation in labour efficiency between farms of similar scale (Hogan et al., 2022), with implications for both profitability and safety outcomes. Investment in facilities and technologies can support farmers to achieve "the 50-hour week" benchmark during peak periods.

Implementation pathway:

- Investment priorities can be specified in Member State National Plans
- The Post-2027 framework provides enhanced flexibility for Member States to target investment support
- Specific provisions for investment support in proposed implementing regulation

Policy reference:

- Articles in proposed CAP implementing regulation relating to investment support
- The Commission's Post-2027 Q&A states that income support "now includes... on-farm investments such as farm modernisation, diversification or the uptake of new practices and technologies"

Specific investment priorities identified in this research:

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- Livestock handling facilities that reduce manual handling and injury risk
- Labour-saving milking and animal care equipment
- Farm infrastructure that reduces travel time and physical workload
- Digital technologies that reduce administrative burden (where appropriate to farm scale)

5.3.4 Replacement Worker and Relief Services

Finding addressed: Finding 2 (Time Poverty); Finding 4 (Cross-stakeholder collaboration)

Recommendation: Member States should consider establishing or expanding replacement worker schemes that enable farmers to take time off for rest, training, health appointments, or family responsibilities without compromising farm operations.

Implementation pathway:

- Such schemes can be supported through rural development interventions
- Cooperation measures can support the organisational infrastructure (e.g., cooperatives, farmer groups providing relief services)
- The French "Service de Remplacement" provides an established implementation model

Post-injury coverage: Replacement worker schemes should be designed to provide emergency coverage following farm accidents, not only planned absences. The intensification dynamics identified in this research demonstrate that when injuries remove farmers from work, increased labour burden on remaining household members creates conditions for secondary injuries. Priority access to replacement services following an injury can interrupt this cycle. The French "Service de Remplacement" provides a model incorporating both planned and emergency coverage.

Policy reference:

- Rural development intervention types in Post-2027 framework
- Cooperation and collective action provisions

Note: This recommendation directly addresses the time poverty mechanism identified in our findings. Farmers cannot attend safety training, access health services, or simply rest if there is no one to cover essential farm operations.

5.3.5 Knowledge Transfer on Work Organisation

Finding addressed: Finding 2 (Time Poverty); Finding 5 (Technology)

Recommendation: The knowledge transfer and innovation support provisions of the Post-2027 CAP should explicitly include work organisation and labour efficiency as priority topics, recognising these as foundational to both farm sustainability and farmer wellbeing.

Rationale: Work organisation has been identified as a key determinant of labour efficiency, with the most effective farms achieving substantially shorter working hours without sacrificing productivity (Hogan et al., 2023). This knowledge can be transferred through advisory services, demonstration farms, and peer learning networks.

Policy reference:

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- The Commission's October 2025 communication states that Member States will be required to provide "accompanying tools that enhance the transition to sustainable and resilient farming, which include qualified advisory services, knowledge exchange, innovation and digitalisation measures"
- Specific Article references for knowledge transfer provisions

5.3.6 Thematic Network on Supporting Farm Households Affected by Injury

Finding addressed: Finding 1 (Hierarchical causal logic—upward consequences and intensification); Finding 4 (Cross-stakeholder collaboration)

Recommendation: The European Commission should fund a Horizon Europe Thematic Network focused on identifying and sharing good practices for supporting farmers and farm households coping with the longer-term burden of injury.

Rationale: The consequences of farm injuries—particularly household labour crises and intensification cycles—are common across diverse European farming contexts. However, support mechanisms vary substantially between Member States, and there is no systematic mechanism for sharing effective practices. A Thematic Network would address this gap.

Network activities:

- Document existing support mechanisms across Member States (social insurance, replacement worker schemes, rehabilitation services, advisory support)
- Identify effective practices for preventing intensification of consequences
- Develop practical guidance materials for farm organisations, advisory services, and social protection bodies
- Create knowledge exchange mechanisms between researchers, practitioners, and farming communities
- Address specific needs of vulnerable groups including women farmers, elderly farmers, and migrant workers

Implementation pathway:

- Call for proposals under Horizon Europe Cluster 6
- Thematic Networks are an established instrument with proven effectiveness for multi-actor knowledge exchange
- The SafeHabitus project and its Communities of Practice provide an existing network that could contribute to such an initiative

Responsible bodies: DG RTD, DG AGRI, EIP-AGRI Service Point

5.4 Tier 3: Vision for Integrated Farm Safety and Wellbeing Support

The recommendations above address specific policy mechanisms within the CAP framework. However, our findings point toward a more fundamental need: the integration of farmer health, safety, and wellbeing as explicit objectives of agricultural policy, alongside productivity, environmental sustainability, and food security.

This vision section outlines what such integration might look like, recognising that full implementation would require action beyond the CAP alone, involving coordination between DG AGRI, DG EMPL, DG SANTE, and national authorities responsible for occupational health and safety, social protection, and healthcare.

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5.4.1 An Integrated Approach to Farm Safety

The current European agricultural policy landscape addresses farmer wellbeing through fragmented mechanisms:

- **CAP** provides income support and investment funding but does not directly address occupational safety
- **OSH Framework Directive (89/391/EEC)** applies primarily to employed workers, with limited reach to self-employed farmers in many Member States
- **Social protection systems** vary substantially across Member States in their coverage of agricultural workers and self-employed farmers
- **Healthcare systems** often struggle to reach rural and farming populations

Our findings demonstrate that these policy domains are interconnected through the mechanism of time poverty. A farmer experiencing income pressure may work longer hours, defer equipment maintenance, skip training, and avoid medical appointments – with consequences for safety, health, and ultimately productivity. Policy interventions in one domain affect outcomes in others.

An integrated approach would:

1. **Recognise time as a policy-relevant resource** – Just as policy considers financial resources and environmental resources, it should consider temporal resources. Measures that demand time from farmers without providing compensating support may undermine their intended objectives.
2. **Establish cross-DG coordination on farm safety** – Farm safety outcomes depend on policy decisions across multiple Directorates-General. A coordination mechanism could ensure that agricultural, employment, and health policy work in the same direction.
3. **Extend OSH coverage to self-employed farmers** – While respecting the principle of self-employment, consideration should be given to how OSH protections can be extended or adapted for self-employed farmers, potentially through social conditionality mechanisms or voluntary frameworks.
4. **Create "right to rest" mechanisms for farmers** – Unlike employed workers, farmers have no institutional mechanisms ensuring rest periods, annual leave, or limits on working time. Replacement worker schemes and cooperative arrangements can provide functional equivalents.
5. **Integrate safety into agricultural education** – From initial agricultural training through continuing professional development, safety should be embedded as a core competency rather than a separate compliance requirement.
6. **Address consequences as well as causes** – Current farm safety policy focuses predominantly on injury prevention. The findings of this research demonstrate that injury consequences cascade through socioecological levels and intensify over time, creating long-term burdens for farm households and communities. An integrated approach would include systematic support for injured farmers and their households, encompassing rehabilitation services, income protection during recovery, and assistance with labour redistribution.

5.4.2 Temporal Framework for Agricultural Policy

Building on the Time Poverty concept developed in this report, we propose that future agricultural policy evaluation should include explicit consideration of temporal impacts:

- **Time impact assessments** for new measures, analogous to environmental impact assessment

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- **Temporal indicators** within CAP monitoring and evaluation frameworks
- **Research investment** in understanding time-use patterns and their relationship to safety, health, and economic outcomes

This represents a paradigm shift from viewing farmers' time as an unlimited resource that policy can draw upon, toward recognising time scarcity as a constraint that shapes how policy is actually implemented at farm level.

5.4.3 Research on Consequences of Farm Injuries

Finding addressed: Finding 1 (Hierarchical causal logic—upward and intensifying consequence patterns)

Recommendation: The European Commission should support research that examines the medium and long-term consequences of farm injuries on farmers, farm households, rural communities, and the agricultural sector.

Rationale: Research on farm safety has historically focused on injury causes and prevention, with limited systematic investigation of how consequences unfold over time and across socioecological levels. The findings of this deliverable demonstrate that consequences flow upward (from individual injury to household labour crisis to community strain) and intensify within levels (creating self-reinforcing cycles of risk). Understanding these consequence pathways is essential for designing effective support interventions.

Research priorities:

- How injury consequences cascade upward through socioecological levels
- Intensification dynamics whereby injuries create conditions that increase risk of subsequent injuries
- The temporal dimension of consequences, from immediate impacts to longer-term effects on household viability and farm succession
- Economic costs beyond direct medical expenses, including lost productivity and effects on sector attractiveness

Implementation pathway:

- Inclusion as a priority topic in Horizon Europe Cluster 6 (Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment) work programmes
- Support for longitudinal studies tracking injured farmers and their households
- Integration of consequence analysis into existing farm safety research programmes

Responsible bodies: DG RTD, DG AGRI, national research funding bodies

Policy reference:

- Horizon Europe Regulation (EU) 2021/695
- Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2025-2027, which includes sustainable food systems as a key strategic orientation

5.5 Summary of Recommendations by Responsible Body

Table 2: Summary of Recommendations by Responsible Body

Responsible Body	Tier 1 (Immediate)	Tier 2 (Post-2027)	Tier 3 (Vision)
European Commission (DG AGRI)	Guidance on FAS content	Time poverty impact assessment in CAP recommendations; Farm Stewardship design	Cross-DG coordination mechanism
Eurostat	Gender-disaggregated data collection	Temporal indicators development	—
Member State Ministries	Strategic Plan implementation; LEADER priorities	National Plan design; Investment priorities	OSH extension to self-employed
National FAS Providers	Time-use in advisory content	Knowledge transfer on work organisation	—
Farm Organisations	CoP participation	Replacement worker schemes	Sectoral agreements on working time
Research Community	Evidence on labour efficiency (ongoing)	Evaluation studies	Time-use research agenda

Policy Document References

The following policy documents have been referenced in these recommendation:

Current CAP Framework (2023-2027)

1. **Regulation (EU) 2021/2115** – CAP Strategic Plans Regulation
2. **Regulation (EU) 2021/2116** – CAP Horizontal Regulation (financing, management, monitoring)
3. **Regulation (EU) 2024/1468** – Amending Regulations 2021/2115 and 2021/2116 (simplification measures)

Post-2027 CAP Proposals (Under Negotiation)

4. **COM(2025) 565** – Proposal for a Regulation establishing the European Fund for economic, social, and territorial cohesion, agriculture and rural, fisheries and maritime, prosperity and security for the period 2028-2034
5. **Proposed implementing regulation** for CAP post-2027
6. **COM(2025) 236** – Omnibus III Simplification Regulation (amending 2021/2115)

Commission Communications

7. **"A Vision for Agriculture and Food"** (19 February 2025)
8. **"The next chapter for the CAP"** – DG AGRI press release, 17 July 2025

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9. **"Questions and answers on the CAP post-2027 proposal"** – DG AGRI, 23 July 2025
10. **"Future CAP proposal aims to protect Sustainability and Resilience in Farming"** – DG AGRI, 24 October 2025

Other Relevant EU Legislation

11. **Directive 89/391/EEC** – OSH Framework Directive
12. **EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025**

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Annex 1: Guidance for completing task 3.2: Understanding the causes and consequences of Farm Health and Safety Challenges.

Task Summary

Task 3.2 Understanding the causes and consequences of Farm Health and Safety Challenges

Leader: TEAGASC.

Supporting partners: ZRC SAZU; Oxfam; BEC; IDELE; VDU; Savonia; LBU; UAK; Teagasc; EULS; SVLFG.

The objective of this task is to identify the root causes and wider consequences of critical farm health and safety challenges identified by 11 Communities of Practice across the EU, as well as potential solutions. This will involve Expert Focus Groups, supported by Expert interviews, which draw on the Socioecological Model to identify the wider social context surrounding farm safety challenges.

The CoP administrator will bring together an Expert Focus Group and/or a series of interviews from their region or country to contribute to the discussion. Participants will complete a virtual or in-person discussion where they identify the causes and consequences of a single critical farm safety and health challenge on a single sub- population of farmers (e.g. farm workers including women, seasonal and migrant workers, children, elderly farmers etc.) impacted by this issue. Participants include farmers from the identified or other populations, and stakeholders, e.g. health professionals, farm safety inspectors, farm advisors, farm/worker support organisations, co-operatives, producer organisations, with detailed knowledge of the causes or consequences of serious injuries for the chosen farming population. Using a simplified analytical framework, CoPs identify the primary Causes, Consequences, and Solutions described in the Focus Groups/Interviews, and apply the Socioecological model.

Task Outline

This task is straightforward but has a lot of flexibility for CoPs and therefore many options in the guidance below. As always, I am here to support you with any answers you need.

Please refer back to this work plan as you read the document.

Desk Study

1. Identify the safety challenge from your needs register
2. Identify a relevant sub-populations of farmers impacted by this challenge
3. Translate the provided Interview Schedule and develop it for your topic.

Recruitment

4. Recruit at least 2 farmers and 2 stakeholders relevant to your topic.

Data Collection and Recording

5. Select a pragmatic data collection strategy: **Online Focus Group recommended.**
6. Ensure this strategy can produce high quality data for analysis (through recording, notetaking, transcribing).

Analysis and Reporting

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7. Code data into the reporting template, identifying important Causes, Consequences, and Solutions.
 8. Select 3+ key extracts, to exemplify the primary Cause, Consequence, and Solution.
 9. Use the Socioecological Model to identify any common themes.
 10. Write up your results as a Technical Note
11. Send the Reporting Template and Technical Note draft to joseph.firnhaber@teagasc.ie

Task Timetable

Teagasc Support	Throughout!	All
Guidance Document	May 21	Mo.29
Desk Study	June	Mo.30
Recruitment	June/July	Mo.30-31
Data Collection	July	Mo.31
Analysis	July - August	Mo.31-32
Code Sheet submitted	July - August	Mo.31-32
TN (long version) Draft 1	August 29	Mo.32
TN Review (Joe)	September	Mo.33
TN Draft 2 (final)	September 30	Mo.33

*This schedule is subject to minor changes after the deliverable 3.2 meeting with project officers in mid-June.

Desk Study

The desk study will prepare you for collecting and analysing data. It is a short task that all other parts of this task revolve around.

1. First, identify 1 relevant safety challenge from your needs register, and 1 farmer sub-population impacted by this issue. Make this selection using the data and knowledge available, and ensure you can justify this choice, as you will do so in the introduction to the Technical Note that will be included in Deliverable 3.2.
2. Next, translate and develop the basic Schedule provided in this document. This schedule provides a generic structure and prompts to get you started in tailoring your schedule to the specific topic, the safety challenge and sub-population, you chose. This is designed to be a semi-structured interview, so you do not need to develop a prompt for every single sub-topic area unless you feel the need to. Report any major adjustments (such as rearranging the conversation) to the schedule in the Reporting Template.
3. Finally, prepare your (very) short introduction segment to the Schedule. This is a national-level overview of your chosen safety challenge and sup-population. This will help the discussion focus on more complex issues and generate new knowledge as a result.
4. For example, Teagasc is focusing on older (65+) farmers machinery safety based on our needs register and national data. Our presentation will overview a few of these numbers to describe the importance of participants' input on this issue, and a few of the known and basic causes and consequences to get the conversation started.

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Recruitment

Recruitment is based around your chosen topic and sub-population, and all of your decisions should be justifiable for these reasons. There is a lot of flexibility so that you can get the participants you need for a good discussion, so report your decisions in the Technical Note and Reporting Template. If in doubt, describe your prospective recruiting strategy with me and I will work with you to help it fit these requirements.

Sample Composition

Your sample **must include 2+ farmers and 2+ stakeholders** to produce several different perspectives from your country and allow for a nuanced analysis. Note that these focus groups and interviews are **not** personal nor do they involve participants' personal experience, so:

- Participants **do not** have to belong to the chosen population.
 - Participants **do not** have to have experience with the chosen safety challenge.
1. Farmers – at least two different farmers with expertise relevant to your topic or population. For example, if your population is Women farmers, you could select a man who is a farm worker, a woman who is a farm manager, and a farmer (of any gender) who is a spouse/family member of a woman farmer to get a variety of perspectives on this issue.
 2. Stakeholders – at least two different stakeholders with relevance to your topic or population. For example, if your topic is mental health, you could get a policymaker, a rural healthcare provider, and a vet/advisor who may all work with farmers in different ways to get a variety of perspectives on this issue.

Sample Size

With the above criteria, your sample size (across interview and focus groups) will be **4 or more**. Some examples of reaching this are:

1. 1 focus group of 8 participants (farmers and stakeholders)
2. 6 interviews (a mix of farmers and stakeholders)
3. 1 Focus Group of 3 stakeholders, and 4 interviews with farmers

Focus groups with more than 10 participants may be hard to manage. Focus groups below 3 may not be as useful conversations and use of your time, and interviews would be easier to organise in comparison. For example, in Ireland, we are shooting for a focus group of around 7 participants (3 farmers, 4 stakeholders) and additional interviews if needed or if time allows.

Data Collection and Recording

For Deliverable 3.2 and for your own TN's analysis section, you need good empirical data. This can include Transcripts, Audio Recordings, or detailed Notes on the conversation. Determine a pragmatic plan to obtain these, using this guidance and your capacity and time constraints. Holding 1 focus group will require more time to organise but less time to analyse. Holding a series of interviews will be much easier to organise but will create more data to analyse. Plan accordingly.

1. Focus groups – I suggest having a note taker present to capture the conversation regardless of format
2. Interviews – I suggest audio recording, as a note taker can interrupt interview dynamics. The facilitator can take detailed notes afterward
3. Online – I suggest using auto-transcription through teams
4. In-person – I suggest producing comprehensive notes or recording and transcribing audio (resources permitting).

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Below are two examples of collecting data using an online focus group and an in-person interview to show how you could apply these recommendations. You can also apply them in other ways (like in-person focus groups or online interviews).

Example Protocol 1 – Online Focus Group

The following methodology is an example for how you can produce both notes and a transcript during an online focus group.

1. Send Consent forms to participants to sign and return.
2. Hold your focus group online on Microsoft Teams.
3. Warn participants that this will be recorded and ask if they consent to this.
4. Turn on recording and Auto Transcription.
5. Have a separate facilitator to run the meeting, and a note-taker to record participants' main contributions
6. After the meeting, the facilitator reviews these notes and adds in any additional notes.
7. Review the auto transcript for accuracy.
8. This focus group's data (Transcript and Notes) is now ready for analysis.

Example Protocol 2 – In-person Interview

The following methodology is an example for how you can produce an audio file and notes from an in-person interview.

1. Hold your interview in a comfortable location, such as a café, residence, or meeting room.
2. Provide your participant with the consent form
3. Warn participants that this will be recorded and ask if they consent to this.
4. Record using an audio recorder.
5. The facilitator conducts the interview.
6. After the interview, make detailed notes.
7. Review the audio recording and record and further relevant details.
8. This interview's data (Notes, Audio recording) is now ready for analysis.
 - a. If you have access to the labour (e.g. Research Assistants) or auto-transcription software, you can transcribe this audio.

Transcribing Audio

Microsoft Word has an effective auto-transcription option where you can upload audio and it will generate the transcription. Your institution may have this option enabled or may be able to enable it for you. This auto transcript will still need to be corrected and cleaned (like any auto-transcription). Only use the option of human transcription if you have an easy way to do so, such as an RA working on your team.

No Audio Recording Possible?

If you are not able to record audio (for example, you are conducting phone interviews or you are working with an in-person focus group where audio recording is too hard to hear) ensure you are able to generate detailed notes during or after the fact as you will not have a 'hard copy' of your data to reference.

Focus Group/Interview Schedule

Run the focus group or interview using your translated and developed Schedule. I've included advice in the Schedule about how to conduct this. If you have any questions about it, or the facilitator is unused to running interviews, please set up a chat with me so that I can help answer questions.

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Obtaining Consent

Make sure that you have participants provide their consent. I have attached a very detailed consent form that we use in Teagasc. You can translate and summarise the most important parts of this. Participants must be informed that their data is recorded and will be anonymised and is confidential. Participants must give their written or verbal consent to participate. I usually email participants the consent form beforehand (for online meetings) or bring it to sign (for in-person meetings).

Semi-Structured Format

These interviews and focus groups are semi-structured. This means that the focus is on participants' descriptions of topics, not on getting specific answers for every prompt. For example, a focus group with very invested participants may cover many of your prompts naturally. This is the ideal situation, and your main role is to keep participants to time and on topic and allow everyone the chance to contribute. On the other hand, participants might be quiet at first, especially in interviews, and you may have to prompt them more. Always ask open-ended questions, like the ones included in the Schedule, to encourage people to share more.

Analysis and Reporting

This analysis is where you address the central research question: identify the causes and consequences of farm safety challenges on key farming populations. You are ready for analysis once you have empirical data: Audio recording, Transcripts, and/or Notes. Our goal is to produce 3 types of data:

1. Codes, consisting of a list of the primary causes, consequences, and solutions
2. Key Extracts which exemplify these codes
3. SEM analysis of the results, identifying important themes and reported in the Technical Note.

This section will briefly cover how to obtain each of these forms of data using a simplified Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA). If you are familiar, please proceed to produce the above data. If you or the team member doing the analytical task is not familiar with qualitative analytical methods, please set up a chat with me so I can help answer questions. I recommend the [Practical Guide](#) to this method as a resource.

The numbers provided (12 key codes, 3 extracts) are only guidelines that allow you to provide several examples and a quote each about causes, consequences, and solutions. If your data allows, **please include more**. Our publications and the deliverable will be much stronger as a result.

Methodology

You report your methodological decisions in the Reporting Template and in the Technical Note. The Reflexivity statement in the Reporting Template is simply to describe who the analyst and facilitator/interviewer are, or who the team is, with respect to the data. This is to maintain methodological transparency for future publications, even though you **don't** need to include it in your TN.

For example, I would write: The analyst and facilitator of interviews and focus groups is a researcher with the Irish agricultural research and education organisation.

Translation

You can translate text at any point you are comfortable in, including at the very end. As long as I receive the reporting template and PA in English.

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Codes

I recommend the coding procedure below. Your final template could include many codes, but I expect at least 12, roughly 4 main causes, 4 main consequences, and 4 main solutions.

1. List each different Cause, Consequence, and Solution participants described. These are your Codes.
2. Add any important details to these, such as their SEM level(s) if relevant.
3. Report this on the Template

You do not have to follow this strictly in order, but move between steps a through c. For example, if you identify participants discussed stress as a major Cause. You then write out all of the different ways participants identified stress as a cause, and at what SEM level (step b). You then name these different Causes (step a) Administrative Stress and Physical stress symptoms on the reporting template (step c).

On the Technical Note outline, you report your coding Results. If you completed transcripts or have digital notes, consider using a Word Cloud to illustrate this along with your summary, and/or a Table of your primary codes.

Key Extracts

Identify the 3 or more most relevant extracts from your recordings or transcripts, or the most meaningful observations from your notes. Select at least an extract that most clearly illustrates participants' main Cause, Consequence, and Solution. You report these 3 extracts in the Technical Note. Any other important extracts you identify you report in the Template, which also allows you to illustrate which of your Codes appears in each extract.

SEM Analysis

This is the primary output and aim of this task. It will provide the country-level analysis of this question for deliverable 3.2. It will then allow me to identify meta-themes across countries. You report your SEM analysis, as well as identifying any central themes across your Causes, Consequences and Solutions, in the Technical Note draft. The bulk of the technical note (see outline below) is for this analysis and your conclusions. This analysis should connect your findings to the SEM (and any other theories that you see connections to). You can use any (non-AI) software or strategy you prefer to conduct this analysis, as long as the end result is reported in the Technical Note.

Analysis and Coding Example

To provide an example of how you can turn codes into analysis, here are the results of one of the pilot interviews I conducted on older farmers' machinery and animal handling injuries, showing two codes for each Cause, Consequence, and Solution, and a brief analysis across all of these:

1. Primary Causes
 - a. Time and attention poverty, Farm Labour shortage
2. Primary Consequences
 - a. Family and farm business economic hardship, Family stress
3. Primary Solutions
 - a. Strengthened farm relief work system, Business/mentoring scheme to bring in young farmers to help older ones
4. Conclusion (Synthesis and SEM interpretation)

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- a. For this farmer, labour on the farm was equivalent to time and ultimately economic viability of the farm. This participant described a cycle where, as farmers try harder to make up the time, they risk their safety, which ultimately puts even more pressure on the farms labour and viability. In this case, an individual/organizational cause (time pressure and farm labour shortage) causes an interpersonal/institutional consequence (economic and stress pressure on farm family) with a policy/community solution to implement in strengthened support programmes for farmers.

If you have any further questions, please email me. If there is sufficient demand and I have sufficient time, I can provide a 1-2 hour workshop with these results in July/early august.

Technical Note 9 Template

This Technical Note is like a small scientific paper on this qualitative research task, following a very familiar format and reporting your case study. The information from this TN will directly contribute to Deliverable 3.2.

- Title
- Authors and Institution
- Introduction (summary of Desk Study)
 - Identification of primary Safety Challenge
 - Relevant evidence, and justification of choice
 - Identification of primary Sub-Population of farmers impacted by these challenges
 - Relevant evidence, and justification of choice
 - Describe any known causes and consequences of this safety challenge in this population (if any) and identify gaps
 - Describe how the aim of this report is to identify the primary causes, consequences, and solutions of this safety challenge for this population
- Methodology (summary of Recruitment and Data collection)
 - Meaningful translation choices or process (instances where the original Schedule text had to be altered dramatically to fit local country contexts)
 - Participant selection and recruitment (short description of participants, organisations, farming background, etc.)
 - Locations and methods of data collection (focus groups, interviews, format, procedure)
- Results
 - Word Cloud Graphic, and/or Table identifying primary Codes.
 - Summary of main results, with primary extract for each
 - Causes
 - Extract
 - Consequences
 - Extract
 - Solutions
 - Extract
- Analysis
 - Overall themes across Causes, Consequences, and Solutions.
 - SEM analysis, and other important theoretical implications of data.
- Discussion
 - New knowledge about causes and consequences identified (how does this research fill gaps identified in the intro and accomplish central goal).
 - New policy, practice, or research implications of these results

Annex 2: Consent Materials

Consent Form

Note: This is the template that we use in Teagasc for interviews. You can use your standard institutional consent form as long as participants can provide written or verbal consent to being recorded, and understand their data is anonymised and confidential.

Focus Group:

Causes and Consequences of Farm Safety Incidents

We invite you to contribute your expert opinion at a focus group on understanding the root causes and consequences of farm accidents and injuries on older farmers. You do not have to have any personal experience with farm safety incidents to participate.

Study Information

Older farmers are a key group of farmers in Ireland, and face high rates of injuries and accidents. However, these farm safety incidents have many causes, and far-reaching impacts in farming families and communities. This focus group is part of the SafeHabitus project, which seeks to improve farm safety across Europe. By participating, you will help us understand how accidents and injuries play out on farms, and how to best prevent them in the future.

This focus group will take around 1.5 hours.

The group will include farmers, stakeholders, and other experts. You will discuss the root causes of farm safety incidents, their wider reaching consequences, and potential solutions to prevent further incidents.

Participation in this focus group is voluntary.

Even if you agree to participate, you may withdraw at any time while participating without any repercussion, and up to 1 day afterwards. You cannot withdraw after this point, as the transcript will be anonymised and your contributions will not be identifiable.

This focus group is confidential, and the privacy of all participants is important. All published results will be completely anonymous. Information collected through this focus group will be used only for the purpose of research leading to publication of reports and academic papers. All identifying information in the focus group will be anonymised during transcription. All data collected through this focus group will be securely stored for ten years after the duration of the project to allow for scientific publication and communication at press, policy, and academic outlets. Then, all information collected through this focus group will be deleted on or before 31 December 2028. Individual transcripts will not be accessed by or shared with anyone outside the project team: David Meredith, Diana van Doorn, John McNamara, and Joseph Firnhaber.

Information concerning personal data

It should be noted that personal data will only be used for the purpose of the study, will be stored securely by Teagasc and not shared outside of the organisation or only shared outside the organisation as specified. Only the minimum amount of personal data necessary will be collected and it will be stored for the minimum period of time required. The Teagasc Data Protection Officer may be contacted at DPO@Teagasc.ie at any stage.

A copy of Teagasc's privacy policy is available at:

<https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/publications/2018/Data-Privacy-Notice-A5-4pp.pdf>

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which provides further information about how Teagasc will process your personal data in connection with the study.

The fully anonymised coded results of this focus group will be published on the SafeHabitus website Knowledge Hub, in addition to an open data depository.

There are no anticipated risks for taking part in this research. However, if you have any questions or concerns regarding this focus group, please contact Dr. Joseph Firnhaber at 0838712648 or joseph.firnhaber@teagasc.ie

Ethical approval has been attained by the Teagasc Social Science Ethics Committee

Please read the following statements and sign below if you agree to participate in the study:

1. I consent voluntarily to being a participant in this study.
2. I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw without having to give a reason by contacting Dr. David Meredith at David.Meredith@teagasc.ie.
3. I have been given sufficient information about this study and have read and understood this information.
4. I understand that all information I provide in this study will be treated confidentially.
5. I understand that all information shared by other participants at focus groups is also confidential.
6. I consent to the use of the data in this study to be used in research and in the further development of the SafeHabitus project's efforts towards farm safety.
7. I understand that personal information collected about me that can identify me will not be shared beyond the study team.
8. I understand the project my data is being used for may generate results or outputs that could be commercialised; however, my personal data will not be commercialised in any way without my explicit permission.
9. I give permission for results of this research to be deposited in an open data repository so it can be shared and used for learning and potentially reused for future research.

Participant signature

Participant name (BLOCK capitals)

Date:

Annex 3: Focus Group/Interview Script

How to use this schedule

This schedule includes the central topics in **green**, example prompts in **red**, and guidelines for conducting the interview. As this is a semi-structured schedule, the aim is to keep participants on-topic to complete all 3 sections – but you will need to adapt this schedule to your needs:

1. Read through this schedule and guidelines, and then complete a translation of the **topics** and **prompts** into the local language.
2. Design any additional **prompts** that you need to conduct the meeting, and adjust anything necessary for your chosen safety challenge and population.
3. Your finished schedule should be comfortable and work for you to keep participants on topic and provide them freedom to explore these topics.

Key:

Section Title

1. **Topic**
 - a. Guidelines
 - i. **Example prompt**

Introduction – Group Specific Challenges – 5-10 minutes

1. **Welcome, introductions, and thank you for attending**
 - a. Go over the norms for the focus group:
 - b. Respect others in the room
 - c. Conversations and participation is confidential
2. **Format of discussion**
 - a. Provide a simple outline of the structure of the focus group/interview and emphasise the topic of the discussion.
 - i. **In this meeting, we will discuss the causes, consequences, and potential solutions to [insert health and safety challenge and chosen group]. The discussion will last no more than 90 minutes.**
3. **Overview of evidence on group-specific safety challenges in country**
 - a. Give a brief (2 slides, or 2 minute introduction) description of the existing knowledge about the chosen health and safety issue for the group. For example, you some simple statistics on the safety issue or population.
 - b. This short overview will help people cut to the **root** and **wider** components of the conversation outlined below, and show how this is an important topic.
4. **Introduction to Socioecological Model**
 - a. Next, provide an overview of the different SEM dimensions to the conversation. This is just to get them thinking. If you're using a PowerPoint, you can just show them a graphic of the SEM. Finishing with one relevant example **to your own topic** as I have here with the tractor step, gives participants the type of information you want from them.
 - i. **With that said, our discussion today focuses on the deeper and wider causes and consequences of these issues for [group]. We're going to try to think through how many different factors could lead to a challenging situation, and how its impacts could ripple out in many ways. To do this, we're going to keep referencing five spheres of influence**
 - ii. **Policy – relevant laws, funding, and regulations**
 - iii. **Community – neighbourhoods, cities, social norms, and culture**
 - iv. **Organisational – workplaces and schools people spend time in**
 - v. **Interpersonal – relationships between friends, family, coworkers.**

D3.2 - Causes and consequences of occupational injuries and ill health among farmers and farm workers

- vi. Individual – personal knowledge, values, and actions
- vii. So, think about the simple event of a farmer is injured falling when a rusted tractor step gives way, think about what could have led to this. What was the farmer doing beforehand, how did the equipment run down, what policies or legislation could have shaped this? Then let's say they have to take a week or more to recover. How does that impact the business, their social network, or the wider community?
- viii. These are just to get us started in thinking about all of the possible angles on this issue, and this will help us when we get to the last topic, solutions, to think about different ways to address this issue.

5. Questions

Section 1 – Root causes of farm safety challenges – about 15 - 30 minutes

1. Causes

- a. Start your discussion with the most important causes and continue prompting people to explore more and other SEM dimensions they have not yet touched on.
 - i. First, I'm going to ask about the causes of [issue] for [group]. Let's start with what do you think the most important cause is?
- b. Continue prompting people to explore further important issues, and think through the wide number of factors. The SEM dimensions that I have in [brackets] below can be swapped out based on whatever is relevant. These are just examples that you can expand on when translating this interview guide:
 - i. So what is another important cause of [issue]?
 - ii. You mentioned [topic], can you tell me a little more about that?
 - iii. What is a [political] dimension to this?
 - iv. We haven't talked much about [interpersonal] causes, how do you think this could lead to [issue]?
 - v. This example you gave is about farmers in general, how do you think this applies to [group] specifically?
- c. As the conversation proceeds, you can use the list below to mark which topics participants mention, and which ones to prompt. Most conversations will focus on 2-3 of these, and that is fine (it is a result)!
- d. Individual level causes
- e. Interpersonal level causes
- f. Organisational level causes
- g. Community/Cultural level causes
- h. Policy level causes

Section 2 – Wider consequences of farm safety challenges – 15 - 30 minutes

2. Consequences

- a. Continue your discussion with the most important impacts and continue prompting people to explore more and other SEM dimensions they have not yet touched on.
 - i. Next, we're going to talk about the consequences of [issue] for [group]. In this discussion, we're going to also think about the short and long-term consequences. So let's start simple, what do you see is the most important consequence?
- b. Continue prompting people to explore further important issues, and think through the wide number of factors. The SEM dimensions that I have in [brackets] below can be swapped out based on whatever is relevant. These are just examples that you can expand on when translating this interview guide:
 - i. So what is another relevant consequence of [issue]?
 - ii. You mentioned the short term impacts of [topic], what are the long-term consequences?
 - iii. You mentioned [topic], can you tell me a little more about that?
 - iv. How do you think this plays out in the [workplace], or business?
 - v. We haven't talked much about [cultural] consequences, how do you think these [issues] impact communities?

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- vi. This example you gave is about farmers in general, how do you think this applies to [group] specifically?
- c. As the conversation proceeds, you can use the list below to mark which topics participants mention, and which ones to prompt. Most conversations will focus on 2-3 of these, and that is fine (it is a result)!
- d. Individual level consequences
- e. Individual level consequences
- f. Organisational level consequences
- g. Community/Cultural level consequences
- h. Policy level consequences

Section 3 – Potential solutions to farm safety challenges – 15 - 30 minutes

3. Solutions

- a. Finish your discussion with discussing the most important solutions to participants. Here, it is less relevant to have people come up with many solutions at different levels of the SEM, than for them to focus on identifying a few meaningful solutions to the issues brought up in Sections 1 and 2.
 - i. Finally, let's talk about what needs to be done. Considering our discussion of the most important causes and consequences, what's one way you can think of to address this?
- b. Continue prompting people to come up with ideal situations, along with how this could be done. For example, if they think safety education is a solution, you could prompt them to discuss how this could be done on farms or off [organisational], or how it could shape social safety norms [community].
 - i. Earlier, you mentioned [topic] as an important [cause/consequence], how can we address that?
 - ii. We've talked a lot about these large-scale solutions, what are some smaller, more immediate solutions?
 - iii. We haven't yet mentioned solutions for the [individual], what needs to be done there?
- c. As the conversation proceeds, you can use the list below to mark which topics participants mention, and which ones to prompt. Most conversations will focus on 2-3 of these, and that is fine (it is a result)!
- d. Individual level solutions
- e. Interpersonal level solutions
- f. Organisational level solutions
- g. Community/Cultural level solutions
- h. Policy level solutions

Wrap-up

4. Summative thoughts

- a. Wrap up the discussion with a few sentences summarising what you see as the main topics discussed, to check with your participants

5. Anything important missing from this discussion

- a. I like to give people a chance to reflect or go back to a thought they had earlier.
 - i. Before we finish, is there anything you didn't get a chance to say earlier, or anything important that we haven't discussed.

6. Thank you and goodbye

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